

Gendering the Academy
and Research: combating
Career Instability and Asymmetries

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GARCIA WORKING PAPERS

18

Workshops for early career researchers: 12 SSH and STEM test institutions

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GENERAL INTRODUCTION

This GARCIA Working Paper ‘Workshops for early career researchers: 12 SSH and STEM test institutions’ presents the collection of the reports on the workshops for early career researchers that were organized in the six GARCIA beneficiaries: Belgium, Iceland, Italy, the Netherlands, Slovenia, and Switzerland. The workshops were organized in two disciplines: Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

The workshops for early career researchers are part of work package 7 of the GARCIA project. The GARCIA Project – Gendering the Academy and Research: combating Career Instability and Asymmetries – is concerned with the implementation of actions in European universities and research centres to promote gender equality and to prevent gender stereotypes and discriminations. Work package 7 focuses on the revealing of gender practices in the construction of academic excellence in recruitment and selection procedures. The construction of academic excellence is especially salient for the early stages of a academic career, as the label of excellence can make the difference between the inclusion or exclusion of researchers in academia. Building on GARCIA working paper n. 2 on the gap between formal and actual criteria (Herschberg, Benschop, & Van den Brink, 2015), and working paper n. 10 on gender practices in the construction of excellence (Herschberg, Benschop, & Van den Brink, 2016), these workshops are developed for prospective candidates in the early stages of their academic career in order to inform them about the criteria for building an academic career.

The aims of the workshops with prospective candidates were threefold. First, to give candidates information about recruitment and selection criteria applied in the selection processes for early career researchers and how the formal criteria can differ from the actual criteria applied when a candidate is selected. Second, to raise awareness about the gendered construction of academic excellence and gender practices in recruitment and selection processes. And third, to discuss with early career researchers how to take the next step in building their academic career.

Workshops are thus designed to discuss the recruitment and selection criteria and processes for early career researchers and how gender practices can play a role in these processes. Each beneficiary reported on the organization, execution and evaluation of these workshops in their national and organizational context. They reported on the challenges and resistances that they encountered either during the organization of the workshop or during the execution of the workshop. Although the basis of the workshops was the same for every beneficiary, national and organizational context factors resulted in several differences between the beneficiaries. For example, in some beneficiaries it was not possible to carry out the workshops in the STEM and SSH department separately. However, these differences resulted in a valuable overview of what the organization of a workshop of this kind entails in different national and organizational contexts. This exemplifies that keeping in mind the context in which the workshop is to be organized is crucial for its effectiveness and success.

The collection of these reports will provide insight into the organization of workshops for early career researchers, challenges, resistances, learning points and the main outcomes of these workshops at six European universities and research centres.

1. BELGIUM

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of organizing reflexive working groups with prospective candidates is to give them some information about the current situation of recruitment in academia to help them to become aware of how recruitment selection processes work. We use two different settings to achieve this goal. We first organised two reflexive workshops, one in the STEM department (ELI) and one in the SSH department (IACCHOS). These workshops gathered a small amount of participants (3/4) that 1/ exchanged their experiences of recruitment as postdoc researcher or PhD student, and 2/ were given information coming from previous Garcia research conducted in UCLouvain about selection procedures.

A second setting was developed only in IACCHOS. We organised a presentation of some results of the Garcia project at destination of all young researchers of IACCHOS that attended a day of formation for young researcher organised by IACCHOS. This presentation reached between 30 and 40 young IACCHOS researchers.

UCL specific context of recruitment

Selection procedures at the postdoctoral level at UCLouvain can take different forms. Tenure-track recruitment procedures are particularly different from non-permanent postdoctoral research or teaching staff member recruitments. Tenure-track recruitments (at the level of “*chargé de cours*” (assistant or associate professor) or “*chercheur qualifié*” (research associate) are the most formal recruitment procedures. It is the only stage of the career for which an official recruitment committee is constituted to assess the scientific quality of the candidates. Non-permanent post-doctoral position generally does not imply the constitution of a selection commission and are often directly conducted by the primary investigator of a research project himself.

Tenure-track recruitment procedures also depend on the scientific career paths that exist. Two career paths exist in Belgian universities: appointment as permanent professor at a university and appointment as permanent research associate at the FNRS (Belgian Funds for Scientific Research). Selection procedures as university professor or as permanent researcher at the FNRS are different.

This recruitment procedure is very formalised and similar in every institute of the UCLouvain. When a position opens, a job advertisement constituted of a precise profile description is widely distributed. In the same time, a local (i.e. within the Faculty where the position is located regarding teaching duties) recruitment committee is constituted. This committee typically gathers 3 or 4 full professors from the Faculty and 2 external members generally coming from abroad. This tailor-made committee examines all the applications received and draws up a short-list with candidates that will be invited to a hearing. After the hearing, the committee produce a ranking of the candidates. This ranking (identifying generally one preferred candidate, in some cases two can be ranked as first) is transmitted to the central authority of the UCLouvain (the rectoral board, composed of the rector and vice-rectors). The rectoral board then invite the first-ranked candidate(s) for a hearing and makes the final decision to appoint the candidate selected

by the local recruitment committee. Generally the candidate selected by the local commission is appointed, but, in some uncommon cases, the rectoral board can decide that the first-ranked candidate does not demonstrate sufficient scientific achievement and decide to close up the procedure and postpone the appointment to the next year.

1.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

1.2.1 SSH Department

Organization of the workshop

We launched a first round of invitations to PhD students, post-doctoral researchers or former PhD students (who graduated in the three last years) from IACCHOS. We contacted 15 people. 6 agreed to take part to the meeting, 5 were not available at the different dates proposed, 2 refused to participate (one because of a too heavy workload at this period, another didn't wanted to address these topics with colleagues but gives us the contact information of his girlfriend who also is a PhD student in IACCHOS and was interested), two did not responded to our invitation. Finally on the 6 who agreed to take part, two didn't attended the meeting. One because of a too heavy workload, the second was ill that day.

In this invitation we presented the Garcia project and explained that the aim of the workshop was to discuss the following issues: 1/ How to get a permanent academic job today? 2/ What are the different ways in engaging with work in research institutions? 3/ We wanted to discuss the difficulties and obstacles that participants to the meeting face in their career. 4/ We wanted to discuss the perceptions of research work environments that the participants have.

The workshop took place on March the 30th 2016.

The four participants have different profiles, they come from three disciplines: economy, sociology and history:

- Participant 1, is a male former PhD student in his mid-thirties. He obtained his PhD in 2013 from UCLouvain. He is at the time of the meeting (and has been doing that since the end of his PhD) lecturer (pay per hour) in different institutions of Higher education (community colleges), director of a public observatory (50% employment contract) and free-lance researcher. He is currently looking for employment as assistant professor in a university. He has one child.
- Participant 2 is a female post-doctoral researcher in his early-thirties. She obtained her PhD in 2012 in UCLouvain. Since then she obtained postdoctoral grants in two different universities (one abroad, and one in Belgium). She is currently invited (pay per hour) lecturer in UCLouvain and in France and consultant (pay per hour) for a prestigious university in the UK. She is in couple with a researcher also working abroad and she is childless.
- Participant 3 is a male (in his mid-twenties) PhD student in the last year of his 4 years grant from the FNRS (fundamental research). He is in couple, childless.

- Participant 4 is a male PhD student (in his mid-twenties), in the second year of his 4 year grant. He has a grant from a public organisation aiming at producing applied research that benefit the development of one of the Belgian regions. He is in couple, childless.

On the 15 invitations we launched, 10 were send to women. Rate of acceptance for women is 10%, while this rate is 60% for men. Even if we are not in a quantitative research settings, this difference in acceptance rate is worth noting.

Content of the discussions

We organized the discussion in three distinctive rounds. In the first one, we asked the participants to present themselves and to talk freely about the topic of this meeting (making an academic career). In the second one, we presented result from previous Garcia investigation about four “*relationships to the scientific career*” that are four ideal-typical modalities of engaging with academic work. Based on interviews made with postdoc researchers in Louvain, we identified 4 types of engagement: “full engagement with work”, “optimistic engagement”, “ambivalent engagement”, and “distant engagement”. In the last round of discussion, we presented the results of another research about the conception of “academic excellence” realised at UCLouvain. Based on interviews made previously with recruitment committee members, we distinguished two different conceptions of what is scientific excellence at UCL. A first one we called the “nomination set of criteria” and a second that we called the “competition set of criteria”. We then asked the participants to comment and discuss this distinction. We asked them if they agreed with this analytical distinction between these two set of criteria that are used to evaluate the scientific quality of a candidate during recruitment procedures.

The first round of discussion was thus devoted to a presentation of the participant and a free discussion about what does it means to work in a university. The less that we can say is that the first two speakers (the two postdoctoral researchers) presented a very negative picture of their working conditions. They highlighted the high pressure they have to face, the numerous sacrifices they have made, and a strong pessimist view on their future possibilities in academia.

The opening speaker began by telling us a strong disappointment he had lived one week before the meeting. He applied for a position as assistant professor in a university, he went through the selection process and achieved to be ranked first by the recruitment committee. His profile was thus send to the central administration of the university where the final examination is done by the rectoral board. The rectoral board decided not to hire the candidate and to leave the position open for one more year. His profile was judged not excellent enough. This is below, how he explained this episode and how he linked it to what excellence is:

“As I understood it [this episode], excellence is very important, we have to be international, and I could say that this university want more to be excellent and to be in concurrence with Oxford, Harvard, MIT or I don’t know what, that looking at the fact that she is anchored in a territory with an history. I have enormous frustration now. (...) for the rectoral board, all that I have done, that is outside the university, is zero. It is not a peer-reviewed article. I

heard that I had not enough publications, but I have 7 articles in peer-reviewed journals plus 15 more in other journals or books. What I think about excellence? I'm sick of this excellence. [*j'en ai ma claque de l'excellence*]. What I see around me, there is a gender effect, but there is also an effect of this excellence seen as a unique pipeline. When you go through it, it crushes people. And I have often thought that the best [researchers] goes out. When I talk to postdocs, there is a lot of people who tell me: '*I do not want to do this anymore, to publish, to apply, to find a postdoc. Give me anything that I can settle somewhere*'. The game has become too much unidimensional" (Part. 1)

Directly after this first talk, the second postdoc researcher took the floor and went in the same direction:

"This resonate a lot with my own experience. It does not feel difficult to be a women, this is not the first difficulty. It is very difficult to make its own place. I have known several disappointments. The argument of excellence, reduced to the dimension of publications has been used against me, but I think that this is an argument that is instrumentalised to justify other criteria that are more ideological. My work is perceived (and I have now a precise confirmation of that) as too much subversive or too much out of the box. (...) There is a lot of arguments based on the idea that excellence is assessed only through peer-reviewed publications, in which I finally engage myself (I have now four publications in major international journals), but now I do not want to apply to FNRS grants anymore. On another hand, teaching experiences and experiences outside university is totally downgraded. I have a huge experience of teaching, with excellent evaluations and this is not valorised at all. I'm disillusioned. I'm considering quitting research despite the fact that I love my job, and that my research topics are, I think, very important for the society. (...) I'm discouraged, and it takes a lot to discourage me, but I have enough to be oblige again and again to prove that what I make makes sense and is important." (Part. 2)

The two PhD students reacted to these two first statements:

"Something that strikes me [after three year as a PhD student] is the insecurity [*précarité*] of the job. Not regarding salaries or financial aspects, but regarding the efforts that are expected of us compared to the prospects that we can have. There is a gap there. There is maybe to many PhD students. The insecurity, people are asked to spend one year there, one other year there, international is compulsory. It looks like researcher are disembodied person, out of a context: '*go abroad for a year, it's not difficult!*' as if researchers are unattached. (...) It is expected that researchers can contempt themselves with six months of contract there and then some more months there. It is striking and not pleasant. (...) I'm not against going abroad, it is certainly very rewarding, but regarding the work perspective that we can have after all these efforts, if it is to be back to zero, which happens often, it is a bit harsh." (Part. 3)

"It is different for me as I'm not yet in a position where I will do career choices, will I achieve it or not? But I heard that funding are rather short. I'm

funded by this administrative agency (...) They are not interested that I publish peer-reviewed articles, they are not interested that I engage in my university, they want that I produce something that they can use for their politics. But I do a PhD, and it could bring me to the postdoc job market, but if I neglect this, I neither will be competent for the academic job market, nor for the job market outside academia. I try to be active on the two sides, not knowing where I go. I find it quite dangerous to say: *'I want to make an academic career'*, because it seems very uncertain. Not knowing where I go, I try to make the two at the same time. It is a lot of work, and I even not sure that it could take the form of excellence in neither situation. (...) I have the impression to be paid by the administrative agency because it is cheaper for them to paid a PhD student than a real employee. I'm financed as a PhD student but they do not really want me to do a PhD." (Part. 4)

In the two last rounds of discussion, around the presentation of some results obtained in previous investigation conducted in UCLouvain for the Garcia project, the participants talked mainly about how they perceive what working in a university means. A first consensus emerged between the participants regarding the strong evolution that universities have known recently and the unpreparedness, or inexistence of support, vis-à-vis these transformations coming from senior professors.

"My PhD director belong to the old system. She was not at all aware of the 'bibliometric imperative'. I was very naïve and very young. I have made my thesis, because I loved my subject, but I have never thought strategically about my PhD. I heard that you used the expression [referring to what another participant said] *'to build my CV'*, I have never done that. (...) My director transmit me very good values, but she said to me: *'I feel sorry that I never prepare you to make a career in the current system'*". (Part. 2)

"My PhD director is very young, he has gone through all that and he is not anachronistic as older professors could be. (...) At the level of my research centre the question of career is inexistent. We have a seminar where the young researchers of the centre talk about methodologies or concrete problems we could face. Senior professors comes by sometimes and when we address the question of research projects evaluation or other stuff, they seems even more lost than some PhD students. They do not know how to rise the chances to get grants. (...) I do not have the impression to receive advice on how to act strategically." (Part. 4)

"I think that in some senior professor there is a moral posture [against excellence] but that goes along with a lack of understanding. They are settled, and they do not understand what does not work now." (Part. 4)

They also criticized the "academic system" as it is perceived and have made some recommendations:

"The system is not made to select the best it is made to select those who are the most ready to make sacrifices: family, a worthy life, to have other activities than work." (Part 1)

“There is not really a graduate school for PhD students, I find that strange, and it shows a certain vision of the importance of PhD students” (Part. 4)

“We have no intellectual formation, no real intellectual formation during the PhD, (...) We have to gain 60 credits, we have three days of formations every year on history, art and archaeology, (...) but they go from Greek pottery to medieval painting, this is interesting but this is not an intellectual formation.” (Part. 3).

Organization of the conference (April the 13th, 2016)

The 13 of April 2016, the IACCHOS institute organised his first “workshop for young researcher”. This event was the first manifestation of a new interest in IACCHOS for the difficulties that young researchers can face. This topic of concern was raised at the IACCHOS board of director since several years by the representatives of the non-permanent researchers in the board. Last year this lead to the designation of a vice-president of IACCHOS responsible of organising activities for young researchers of the institute.

This one day long workshop was the first event organised by this “young researcher appointee”. Several topical sessions were organised. In the morning the topic was: How to valorise his research, through publication and in other ways? In the afternoon, the topic was: “how to build an ‘attracting’ CV on the postdoctoral job market?”

We asked the organiser if we could integrate a presentation of some result of the Garcia project in this workshop, which she agreed. We were offered a 45 minute presentation at the end of that day.

During our presentation (attended by approximately 30-40 PhD students and researchers) we presented 20 PowerPoint slides presenting the main results of investigation conducted at UCLouvain about the leaky pipeline phenomenon, gender asymmetries in UCLouvain, the different ways of engaging in academic work we identified, and the different criteria that are used in recruitment committee at UCLouvain.

1.2.2 STEM Department

Organization of the workshop

It was more difficult to gather young researchers from ELI than it was the case for IACCHOS. We launched a first round of invitations using the official mailing list of the institute. This invitation was thus sent to all non-permanent researchers (phD students, postdoc, research assistants...) of ELI. We do not know precisely the number of non-permanent researchers of ELI but the invitation reach between 100 and 150 researchers. Only 3 researchers answered this first invitation and have shown an interest in the project. We thus tried to contact several researchers directly through an individual email. We contacted approximately 40 researchers of ELI directly, 1 answered us that he was interested. One of these researcher then convinced two of his colleagues that participation at our workshop would be interesting.

It was not possible to find a date that arranged all the 7 researchers interested, we finally achieved to gather 3 researchers on the 6th of June.

The three participants have different profiles, they come from two disciplines: physics and ecology:

- Participant 1 is a female postdoc researcher. She is in her early-thirties. She got her PhD in the Nederland in 2011. She then got several post-doctoral grants in France and in the US and is now postdoctoral researcher at the FNRS in UCLouvain. She is in couple with one child.
- Participant 2 is a male postdoctoral researcher in physics and climatology in his late twenties. He got is PhD from UCLouvain in 2015.
- Participant 3 is a male postdoctoral researcher in physics and climatology in his early thirties. He got is PhD from UCLouvain in 2014 and previously studied in France.

Content of the discussions

As it was the case in IACCHOS, we organized the discussion in three distinctive rounds. In the first one, we asked the participants to present themselves and to talk about the topic of this meeting (making an academic career), but, and it was not the case in the IACCHOS workshop, we firstly presented some insight from the Garcia project about the leaky pipeline phenomenon and the concept of “greedy institution”. In the second one, we presented result from previous Garcia investigation about four “*relationships to the scientific career*” that are four ideal-typical modalities of engaging with academic work. Based on interviews made with postdoc researchers in Louvain, we identified 4 types of engagement: “full engagement with work”, “optimistic engagement”, “ambivalent engagement”, and “distant engagement”. In the last round of discussion, we presented the results of another research about the conception of “academic excellence” realised at UCLouvain. Based on interviews made previously with recruitment committee members, we distinguished two different conceptions of what is scientific excellence at UCL. A first one we called the “nomination set of criteria” and a second that we called the “competition set of criteria”. We then asked the participants to comment and discuss this distinction. We asked them if they agreed with this analytical distinction between these two set of criteria that are used to evaluate the scientific quality of a candidate during recruitment procedures.

We will not make a compressive account of the content of the discussion. But it is interesting here to emphasis the way in which these three postdocs explained how they feel about their current position. In this regard, the third participant (first speaker) totally agreed with the presentation we made about university being greedy institution. He explained us why he decided to stop research in short term. The second participant is sitting on the fence, and the third one also consider quitting quickly if she do not find a permanent position soon.

At the same time they all agreed to say that they love science, and that they would be really happy if they were granted a permanent position today. The following excerpts from the recording of the workshop give a more detailed description of the views of the participant on looking for a permanent position, or quitting academia:

“This productivity system [in universities] is constantly in contradiction which what is excellence. Unless you are a genius, and it is not everyone, this productive system makes that we degrade the quality of the science we produce. With my PhD, I published 5 papers. If I had kept the most important part to makes only one, it would have been very good. But we are constantly pushed to publish quickly, thus we publish things we are not satisfied with. It is a negative circle, if you are not satisfied with what you do, you loos motivation. Finally I realize that this is still like that after the PhD. I’m in postdoc. It was a test for me to know if it was going to have more appeal to me that the PhD. And the answer is no. (...) for me excellence cannot be achieved or, you are a genius and you can do everything, but I do not think that that is 80% of the researchers. This is the reason why I do not want to go on with research. My ambition, is to work for a living and not to live for my work. (...) today, I’m almost disgusted by research. I even decided to not apply for a position as assistant professor, even if I love teaching, (...) and I know I had my chances for that position.” (Part. 3)

The second presented his own view.

“When I was PhD student, there was the graduation that was an incentive to do what I had to do, now, as postdoc, I confess that I’m less motivated to come to work on week-end, because I know that my contract end in two years and It will be up to me to “beg”, and it is a strong word, for other funding to be able to continue. Normally if I do good work I could expect to be promoted, at least I think this is the case in the private sector, here every time, the fact to be good, only allows me to scrounge for funding.” (Part. 2)

The last one presented her experience:

“What I think is the main hurdle for me to continue in science now. Actually there are several. Obviously the publication of course that I think is enormous. Even if you have publication in international journal, then the next question of the committee will be: *‘well, what is going to be your next publication?’* (...) They are not looking at what you have done, they are just looking at the impact factor and that’s it. For me it seems that way. And then, to get a permanent position, I think in Belgium. But also in the Nederland, not in France actually, the teaching is also very important. (...) it’s difficult because when you do a postdoc you’re supposed to do research, you’re not supposed to do teaching, but then when you are evaluated for a job they say: *‘yeah, but you do not have any teaching experience’*. (...) Basically you need to be able to do everything and it is simply not possible to do everything. I think when I was a PhD student I spent two years coming every week-end to the labs to do my experiments, we did really great things, and I was so happy doing that. And still, I don’t mind sometimes coming the week-end, but now I have a baby, so I’m not going to spend all my week-ends going to the lab. It just not the same anymore.” (Part. 1)

“I applied to a lot of permanent positions. Like 20 applications in two years’ time. I got invited to a couple of interviews, which was very nice. (...) And then last year, I was in ... and obviously I met all my competitors, you are all

there on the same day to make your presentation. They had invited three younger researchers including me and two women, they are very for equal opportunity in the UK, (...) I think that the person who got the job, she had 7 years more experience than me, of course she had postdocs and PhD's so you think: how is it even comparable? Competing with people it seems so unrealistic." (Part 1).

In the three case, the future is seen as very uncertain. The pressure on publication is perceived as enormous by these three postdocs, and this pressure is not seen as healthy nor for the individual life of the researcher (it pushes people to consider quitting science) or for the general functioning of science.

1.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

When performing the two workshops and the conference, our main objective was to create a learning environment by raising the awareness on evaluation criteria that are used in recruitment procedure. We decided to organise reflexive workshop where a lot of room was given to discussion between the participants and where they can share their experiences and perceptions of recruitment procedures.

We will now evaluate the two workshops with this objective in mind. We will identify 1/ what have worked when performing the working groups, 2/ what challenges and resistances we encountered, 3/ what learning points we gain from planning the working groups and 4/ The specificity of the UCLouvain context and what future action could be undertaken.

What worked when performing the working groups?

The way we structured the discussions, with three rounds of discussion around the presentation of previous research results of the Garcia project was very effective. It sparked fruitful discussions in both working groups (ELI and IACCHOS), and permitted to clearly to trigger exchanges of perception between the participants.

The format of the working groups: 4 participants, 2 hours, 3 members of the Garcia project to lead the discussions was plainly effective. The experiences conducted show that, as it was the case for the workshop we organized with committee members, 3 or 4 participants could be an efficient amount of participants for a two hours working groups. Every participant could talk approximatively 20 minutes and a sufficient amount of time was still available for a debate between participants. More crowded working groups would certainly have given less time for collective discussion.

We used two strategies to contact potential participants. In ELI we first tried to use collective mailing list as a way to reach young researchers of ELI. This does not worked. We then decided to contact researchers personally which was more efficient. We actually were surprised by the actual response rate to the first wave of invitations in ELI (4 answers out of more than one hundred invitations). It was much more complicated to gather young researchers for a workshop than gathering senior professor from ELI. In IACCHOS, as we are much more involved in this institute, it was much easier to target

directly people that would be interested in the workshop. We only send 15 invitations and got 13 answers. This is due to our proximity with this institute.

What challenges and resistances we encountered?

The most difficult challenge was to find a date for the workshop. Postdoctoral researcher have to face important workload and have to prioritize their activities. It seems, that for some of them, (and certainly a lot of them in ELI) participate to a workshop that is not directly linked to their research is not a priority. Moreover some of the researchers interested were abroad during the period.

Another difficulties is the language used to communicate information. In IACCHOS, the main language in use is French. Researchers that do not have an excellent command of the French language are very rare. It seems not to be the case in ELI. A possible explanation to the very low rate of interest in ELI is maybe located in the fact that some postdoctoral researchers do not speak French fluently and thus didn't feel concerned by this activity conducted mostly in French (however, in the Eli workshop, one of the participant spoke in English and it was not a problem as all participants and Garcia member were fluent in English).

Another challenge we faced lies in the fact that almost all the participants to our workshops had very pessimistic views on their future. Uncertainties are very high and it was thus difficult to address the question of good practices or of example of achievement in finding a permanent position. For our participants, it almost seems impossible to find one. The discussion were dominated by emotion like frustration, disillusionment, disappointment, and even "disgust". We can fear that these two workshops have reinforced these feelings amongst participants seeing that other postdoctoral researchers have made the same experience and share the same negative perceptions.

What learning points we gain from performing the working groups?

Through the discussions, we gained strong and valuable insight on how postdoctoral researchers perceive their future. This is very interesting for our analytical objective, to see that the analysis of university as greedy institution, and on the evolution of universities toward new work rationalities were very in line with the way postdoc researchers and PhD students perceive there situation.

Through these workshop we could see that organizational transformation of universities have strong negative impact on the subjective life of young researchers. The main topics of concern were 1/the notions of uncertainties and 2/the pressure to productivity that seems somehow incompatible with those prevailing uncertainties. In the view of some researchers, pressure to productivity, if goal are achieved, should be linked to possible rewards or promotions, but in the current academic system, even if you succeed to be very productive (that is mainly publish a lot in 'good' journals), you are never sure to be rewarded, you can only "beg" or "scrounge" for small amount of money for doing your job.

What was specific for our context, which future working group leaders need to take into account?

We think that, beside the question of language used, the context of postdoctoral and PhD student in UCLouvain is not particular different of the context encountered in other institutions or in other European countries. This workshop setting could be easily duplicated in other context as a way to enhance the sharing of experience between young researchers.

1.4 CONCLUSION

The situation in ELI and in IACCHOS was to some aspect very similar. The young researchers we encountered faced strong uncertainties. Most of them think that they will leave science on a short term period, some feel strongly disappointed or even “disgusted” by the system they are in.

The researchers of both institute criticize strongly what is conceived as “excellence” in academia. Most agreed to say that the unidimensional view that excellence can be assessed through publication is not a good thing. In both institutes, researchers presented their experiences in recruitment procedures. And explained that for them, strategies aiming at enhancing his/her own CV, like publication strategies that emphasis the quantity of articles and not the quality of research, or the impact of a journal rather than the content of a research is not positive, nor for them or for science. The prevalence of this discourse on publication strategies even pushes some researchers to leave academia.

In both workshops it was felt that recruitment procedure were unfair. That when a candidate have strong research profile, selection committee ask them why they do not have sufficient teaching experience and on the opposite when they are very strong in teaching, it is perceived as non-important. Postdocs in our workshop have the perception that they have to be “good in everything” and they feel (or they know) that this is not possible, excepted maybe for “geniuses”. That led one of the participant to say that: “he has not the good personality to be a researcher” (ELI, part. 2).

As these very critical stances on “excellence” were the main rationales that we harvested from the researchers taking part to our workshops, it was very difficult to gives them tricks and tips on how to enhance their CV or on how to fulfil what they perceive as the “expectations” hanging over them. All the postdocs that have participated to our workshop are very aware of these strategies. At some point, even one young PhD student noted that, to his view he was more aware on the “new” academic rules of the game that more senior professors of is research centre that show, according to him, a “lack of understanding”.

2. ICELAND

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the workshop was to create awareness among PhD students on how to prepare for a career after completing a PhD degree and learn about the different career areas open for PhD graduates. There were three goals for the training, firstly to raise awareness that there are very few job openings within the University of Iceland and open up the discussion on opportunities outside of academia. Secondly, to assist PhD students who want to pursue an academic career to become aware of how the evaluation and selection processes and practices at the University of Iceland and train them to deal with those criteria. Thirdly, to guide PhD students in building flexible career capital and to prepare applications for job openings outside of academia.

The GARCIA team conducted the workshop in cooperation with the School of Social Science and the University of Iceland Student Counselling and Career Centre. The School of Social Sciences offers a similar workshop for its PhD students, with the main focus on skills that are useful for the progress of the students PhD programme. The workshops have been held monthly for the past years; however the workshop has not been running in the year 2015-2016 due to low attendance. To our best knowledge no similar workshops exist in the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences. The University of Iceland Student Counselling and Career Centre offers workshops on CV writing and on preparing applications for job openings. However, these workshops have first and foremost been aimed at students on bachelor and masters level. Hence, the Student Counselling and Career Centre was quite happy with the cooperation, and saw it as an opportunity to extend their services to the PhD students. The novelty of this workshop was the focus on preparing the PhD students for a career after completing a PhD degree, both within and outside of academia. This is a topic, especially the one regarding career outside of academia, that is on top of the mind of many PhD students but seldom discussed within the academic institution. In order to make the workshop sustainable it was important to cooperate with the University of Iceland Student Counselling and Career Centre, build on the existing knowledge, and make the workshop applicable to the other academic schools at the University of Iceland. Hence, it was considered good practice to design and conduct one workshop for the PhD students at the School of Social Sciences and the PhD students at the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences, which could be extended to other fields in the future. Furthermore, with the results of task 7.1 and 7.2 being similar for the School of Social Sciences and the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences it seemed fit for task 7.4.2 to bring together the PhD students of both Schools. This however results in a shorter report from the Icelandic GARCIA team.

2.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

2.2.1 STEM and SSH department: The School of Engineering and Natural Sciences and the School of Social Sciences

All PhD students in the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences and the School of Social Sciences were invited to participate in the workshop, originally advertised to be conducted in Icelandic. An invitation was sent to 145 PhDs in the School of Engineering

and Natural Sciences and 94 PhDs in the School of Social Sciences on April 12th 2016. An reminder was sent on April 18th 2016 and information that the workshop would be conducted in English, following a request from a PhD student in the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences. In attempt to attract PhD students the workshop was organised on a Friday afternoon, at 14:30 – 16:00, followed with a reception. In total 18 PhD students participated in the workshop, 15 from the School of Social Sciences and three from the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences. Majority of the participants were women (13 from SSH and 1 from STEM), but only four male PhD students attended the workshop (two from SSH and two from STEM).

The workshop was set up as a seminar with four presentation. The first presentation was on the outcomes of tasks 7.1. and 7.2, and the three following presentations were seen as training for the PhD students on how to build a career within and outside of academia. Questions and comments were taken after each presentation. However, few questions and comments were received at the workshop but a lively informal discussion took place in smaller groups in the reception afterwards. Lack of questions during the workshop could be explained with the workshop being conducted in English, while the informal conversation all took place in Icelandic.

Dr. Tamar M. Heijstra, an assistant professor working in the GARCIA project, presented the research results on academic recruitments. The aim of her presentation was to create awareness among PhD students on the criteria used in recruitment, selection and evaluation processes and the practices at University of Iceland. Dr. Heijstra presented the formal and the actual selection criteria in the selection process of assistant professor positions and demonstrated actual practices in the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences and the School of Social Sciences. In her presentation she raised awareness on how evaluation criteria are not objectified truths, how evaluators' conceptions of 'quality' differ, and how gender practices influence the selection process and the selection criteria including conceptions of excellence. The PhD students did not ask questions during the presentation, even though they were encouraged to do so. However, they showed great interest in the results in the reception/social gathering afterwards, especially the subjectivity of the criteria and the gendered aspects of the selection processes. Furthermore, some students shared their gratitude on opening up the discussion on few career opportunities within the University of Iceland an issue that has up until now not been confronted within the academic institution.

Jónína Kárdal, from the University of Iceland's Student Counselling and Career Centre talked about transferable skills and professional reputation. Her presentation focused on CV-writing and how to prepare applications for job openings outside of academia. Ms. Kárdal encouraged the PhD candidates to identify their skills, map their strengths and work towards building a flexible career capital and transferable skills. Furthermore, she encouraged the PhD students to visit the Career Centre and use the services provided, such as receiving a help from counsellors with writing CV's, career portfolios and cover letters. A PhD student opened up the discussion on the risks of being too self-gratulatory in cover letters. This enabled an interesting conversation of the importance of self-promotion and honesty. In the reception afterwards some PhD students shared how Ms. Kárdal presentation was eye opening for opportunities outside of academia and a positive inspiration.

Hulda Proppé is the Research Manager of the School of Social Sciences, her presentation focused on research opportunities for PhD graduates who want to work within academia and in research. The presentation was on the importance of producing and disseminating excellent research, gathering teaching experience, understanding the discipline, understanding the academic sector and understanding the labour market. Ms. Proppé gave the PhD students tips on how to make an impact within their discipline, by publishing, by aiming for quality not quantity, by having good references and start early to think about collaborations and interdisciplinary cooperation. She encouraged PhD student to set goals and mark out actions on how to achieve these goals. Furthermore, Ms. Proppé gave information on national and international funding opportunities open for PhD graduates and how to look for academic vacancies internationally. She stressed the importance of PhD students extending their network and mentions that it is essential for those who want an academic career, and shared tips and tricks on how a PhD student can extend his/her network.

Dr. Ásta Bjarnadóttir, Chief Human Resources Officer at Landspítali the University Hospital and PhD in Industrial and Organizational Psychology, gave a talk about post PhD career options in the private sector from her own experience. Because PhD holders from STEM, working outside of academia, are more visible than PhD holders from SSH it was considered very important to have a presentation from a successful PhD holder from SSH. In her inspirational talk Dr. Bjarnadóttir talked about the increasing opportunities outside of academia, both nationally and internationally, and that PhD candidates are very valuable assets for the labour market. She encouraged the PhD students to be confident about their skills, make those skills transferable and to think outside the box, and shared her experience of creating the jobs she has wanted. Dr. Bjarnadóttir received questions in relation to her position as a Chief Human Resources Officers on the evaluation of the criteria 'social skills'. In her view that criteria is highly important, and she stressed the importance of addressing it and being candid if a candidate has encountered problems during his/hers PhD or career, such as a fallout with a supervisor.

2.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

2.3.1 STEM and SSH department: The School of Engineering and Natural Sciences and the School of Social Sciences

When considering what worked when planning and performing the working groups there were four main elements that made the task successful. First, it was important to focus on careers inside and outside of academia. The results of task 7.1 and 7.2 show that there are little chances for a full-time permanent position within the University of Iceland for PhD graduates from University of Iceland, therefore it was important to create awareness and prepare the PhD students to face this reality. Second, it was important to collaborate with the University of Iceland's Student Counselling and Career Centre. We think it is important that a formal governing body within University of Iceland offers these services to the PhD students, and the Career Centre was very interested in reaching out to this group of student. We believe by building a platform between the early career academics and the Career Centre, the early academics have a place to seek guidance and support when building a career after the termination of their PhD programme. Third, it was very important that a successful PhD holder, who has a career

outside of academia, did a presentation on tips and tricks concerning the labour market outside of academia. We believe that Dr. Ásta Bjarnadóttir was an inspiration for the early career academics and opened up possibilities that weren't maybe visible for some PhD Students before the meeting. Fourth, it was very positive to have Ms. Hulda Proppé give insight into the national and international funding market and international career opportunities for those early career academics that are aiming for a career within academia. We believe her tips and tricks will guide prospective candidates on how to make the most of their PhD programme and prepare them for the career that awaits them after graduation.

The PhD candidates described in informal conversation in the reception after the workshop that it was important to start a conversation about the low chances of a position for UI PhD graduates within the University of Iceland. The candidates were, however, very positive and saw the presentations as useful instruments on how to go on with their PhD programme and to build their careers. Furthermore, the PhD candidates were positive on the discussion on the gender practices and how excellence is constructed in the selection process. Some PhD students shared how the outcomes of task 7.1 and 7.2 fits their feelings about recent appointments within the University. Others saw these results as useful tips on how to make the most of their PhD programme and build a scientific career within the University of Iceland. This information is however built on informal conversations the GARCIA group had with the PhD students in the reception after the workshop. Future workshop leaders should get a more formal feedback from the PhD candidates, that can be done with a short online survey on the workshop.

Furthermore, we believe that it was a very positive to bring together the PhD students from the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences and the School of Social Sciences. The Schools are not only very similar in term of the construction of excellence in the selection process, but we think it is good for PhD students in both Schools to see their individual position in a bigger context. There is an idea an PhD programme in the School of Social Sciences should be a lone working process and even a lifetime's work, while the PhD programme in the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences is seen as being more pre-defined and based on co-operation, and therefor the programme can be finished in a relatively short time. We believe that the workshop can take part in deconstructing ideas about the School's PhD programmes, and that the candidates can compare and contrast with each others and have a realistic expectations about their programmes. Some PhD candidates revealed their surprise on the matter in informal conversations after the workshop.

The biggest challenge in planning and performing the workshop was to get the PhD candidates to participate. In attempt to attract more participants, the workshop was arranged on a Friday afternoon, followed with a reception. It did, however, not result in good attendance. This reflects a reoccurring problem when it comes to PhD students, at least within the School of Social Sciences, where there is generally very poor attendance to meetings and the monthly workshop for the School's PhD students. This has resulted in the monthly workshop being cancelled during the winter of 2015-2016. Future workshop leaders have to take this into account, and we believe that it is important to reach the PhD candidates with a different method. Possibly through the PhD student associations that are active in both schools. It is important to mention that when

preparing for this workshop we were in good contact with the student association at the School of Social Sciences.

Another challenge, that might be considered a common problem in Icelandic society, was to get the PhD students to take part in the conversation during the workshop. Future workshop leaders have to take that into account, find ways to make the workshop more interactive. A good example on this problem from the workshop was when Dr. Proppé started her presentation she asked the PhD students to raise their hand if they were considering a career in academia. The PhD students were very hesitant and very few raised their hands. The hesitation could, however, be explained with the PhD students being realistic or them being cautious about raising their own expectations. The low chances of getting a position, especially within SSH, is highly visible within the University of Iceland. The hesitation could furthermore be explained with the workshop being conducted in English. Most PhD students have Icelandic as a first language, and we have a feeling they are insecure with speaking up in English at meetings and workshop such as this one.

2.4 CONCLUSION

We see the workshop as a feasible instrument for the University of Iceland to raise awareness among the PhD students on their career opportunities after the termination of their PhD programme. The workshop can serve as a practical instrument for the PhD students on how to go on about their studies in relation to future aspirations, inside or outside academia, after the completion of their PhD program. The PhD students that are aiming for a career within academia are after a workshop like this one better prepared for the evaluation and selection processes and practices, more aware on where to seek opportunities after the completion of their PhD programme and able to aim at building a successful career based on what is known to be considered 'excellent'. The PhD student that see more opportunities outside of academia will gain access to specialists and instruments at the Career Centre and tips and trick on how to build a successful career. We believe that future workshop should be conducted by the the University of Iceland's Student Counselling and Career Centre in co-operation with all the academic schools. A workshop like this one should be conducted once a year and should be made mandatory for first year PhD students.

3. ITALY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of this report is to describe and reflect on the implementation of the activities (workshops and individual colloquia) targeted to prospective candidates for tenured academic positions performed in the two GARCIA beneficiary departments – the **Department of Sociology and Social Research (DSRS)** and at the **Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science (DISI)** – at the University of Trento (UNITN).

At the DISI, we organised a workshop with postdocs, research fellows and PhD students conducted by three external consultants: Bianca Elzenbaumer from the Leeds College of Art; Fabio Franz from the Sheffield School of Architecture; and Maurizio Teli, who was postdoc at the DISI and currently works at the Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute. At the DSRS, we organised a workshop and individual colloquia with postdocs and PhD students, conducted by prof. Barbara Risman from the University of Illinois at Chicago and visiting professor at UNITN.

Moreover, at the University level, we collaborated with the Scientific Research and Technological Transfer Division of the University of Trento organizing a training course on the ERC Starting Grant selection procedures.

The aim of these interventions was to reflect on/to analyse: a) the evaluation criteria and practices adopted in academic selection/recruitment processes, b) the mechanisms that can foster the reproduction of gender inequalities, gender biases and disparities in academic career development, c) the mechanisms, events, features which can trigger the accumulation of advantages in career development in academia.

The report consists of two parts: the set-up, and the evaluation of each intervention.

Before moving to the presentation of the two interventions, we will provide a brief description of the specific context of the UNITN and of the two GARCIA beneficiary departments considering the gender unbalance along the career ladder and trends in the presence of postdocs and PhD students.

The UNITN is one of the Italian universities with the lowest presence of women among its research and academic staff. In 2014, the proportion of women in the university's entire academic staff (full, associate and assistant professors, postdocs) was 29.7%, while the Italian average was 40.5%. Both the Garcia beneficiary departments are strongly unbalanced in terms of sex distribution along the academic ladder. The lack of women is particularly visible among the top positions: at the DISI there were no female full professors while at the DSRS they were only 2 at the end of 2015. Moreover, in both cases, the level of feminization of the academic staff is systematically lower than the national average of the related academic fields (Ferri et al. 2016).

Considering the target population of the activities described in this report, the incidence of postdocs at the UNITN reached 34.4% of the university research staff, which is about 5 percentage points higher than the Italian average at the end of 2014. In the case of DISI the incidence of postdocs was 57% at the end of 2015, while at the DSRS the incidence of these positions were 35.5% of the department research staff.

Focusing on the gender composition of postdocs, at the DISI there are only 13 females out of 57 postdoc researchers at the end of 2015. Interestingly, the total number of the DISI's postdocs has almost doubled between 2012 and 2015, but this growth has been fed by the number of male postdocs, while the number of female postdocs has remained almost stable over time. In the case of the DSRS, female postdocs usually outnumber male of one of two units. At the end of 2015, out of 8 postdocs 5 were women.

The DISI has also an unusual high presence of PhD students. In 2015, they were 151, which means almost one fourth of the overall doctoral students hosted at the University of Trento in 19 doctoral programs. Some of the PhD grants are awarded by research foundations and companies. Given the high number PhD students, the Doctoral School's committee, made up of doctoral student advisors, consists of 60 participants from other Italian and foreign universities or research centres (Murgia et al 2015). However, the presence of women among PhD student is quite limited. In fact, female PhD students are only 38 (25.2%). On the contrary, the doctoral program in Sociology and Social Research counted 19 PhD students at the end of 2015 and the sex composition was quite balanced: 9 male and 10 female.

3.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

The main objective of this intervention was to empower early career researchers, and especially female researchers, in preparing applications for an assistant professor position. The principal aim was, thus, to create awareness among early career researchers on the criteria used in recruitment, selection and evaluation processes and practices in universities and train them to deal with those criteria.

More precisely, we wanted to create a learning environment by organising workshops for prospective candidates and non-tenure researchers to raise awareness on how gender practices influence the selection process and the selection criteria, including conceptions of excellence. In particular, part of our goals was also to raise awareness that evaluation criteria are not objectified truths, and that evaluators' conceptions of criteria differ.

The goal of training early career academics (PhD candidates and postdoctoral research fellows) was to help those researchers who want to pursue an academic career to become aware of how the recruitment and selection process works in their field and to better prepare them to face these practices.

The target group for this intervention were prospective candidates for tenure-track or permanent positions of the GARCIA beneficiary departments at UNITN: DISI and DSRS.

Given the wide differences between the two departments in terms of gender composition, career development chances, research networks, level of

internationalization (see: Bozzon et al. 2015; Peroni, et al. 2015; Murgia et al. 2016), two different actions were implemented with early stages researchers in the two GARCIA beneficiary departments at UNITN:

- 1) The first involved PhD candidates, postdocs and research fellows from the DISI and other STEM disciplines and it took place on May 24th, 2016.
- 2) The second involved as well PhD candidates, post docs and research fellows from the DSRS, and it took place in different moments: a workshop was organised on June the 13th, 2016 and then individual colloquia were realised between June 13th, 2016 and June 24th, 2016.

In the next paragraphs we will detail the set-up process of the two interventions.

3.2.1 STEM department (DISI)

In the case of the DISI, we decided to create a learning environment by organising a workshop with potential candidates and other key players from an international environment. The decision to implement this workshop involving a plurality of actors from different contexts, was led by the strong internationalised structure of the Department, whose primary aim is to develop knowledge in the areas of the ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) adopting interdisciplinary approaches and involving stakeholders from all over the world. Thus, due to the global context in which the department operates, it was important to involve early career researchers of the department and, at the same time, to place the discussion in consideration of the international job market dynamics. In such environment, we believed that it was very important to explore the precarization of work in academia and its intersections with the gender dimensions, analysing its significant consequences in terms of development of a research line and of researchers' wellbeing.

In organising the training, our main concern was to identify a period over the academic year not saturated by teaching and research duties in order to guarantee the participation of a consistent number of early career researchers. For this reason, in the organisational process, the workshop took place during COOP 2016 - XII International Conference on the Design of Cooperative Systems (<http://www.coop2016.unitn.it/>) – held in Trento between May 22th and May 28th 2016.

Figure 3.1. Screenshot of the description of the GARCIA session within the COOP conference website

As explained in the GARCIA working paper on “Reflexive working-group with committee members” (Bozzon et al. 2016) during the conference we decided to organise three different moments: a reflexive working groups with committee members, the workshop for prospective applicants and a plenary session in order to present all the results to the whole audience of the conference (more than 60 people belonging to the DISI department and the COOP conference attendees).

COOP is one of the key European conferences on Cooperative Systems, Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW) and Collaborative Computing and it is affiliated to EUSSET – the European Society for Socially Embedded Technologies. COOP 2016 was the twelfth edition of this biennial conference and took place for the first time in Trento, Italy, organised by the DISI and the Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK). The COOP conferences promote the idea that cooperative systems design requires a deep understanding of collective activities, involving both artefacts and social practices, within a context.

This year, the programme intended to open up to the topic of collaborative design, with a special emphasis on “Making together”. In our opinion it was a great opportunity to involve the DISI community, in such an open environment, with an intimate setting, facilitating in-depth discussion and feedback in a multi-disciplinary community. The workshop we hosted, thus, was named “Making academic careers together. Recruitment, precariousness and gender” (<https://www.eventbrite.it/e/biglietti->

making-academic-careers-together-recruitment-precariousness-and-gender-afternoon-session-23420158324).

The session involved PhDs, post-docs and research fellow of the University of Trento, in particular from the DISI and other STEM departments, and the COOP community. The target group for this intervention were prospective candidates for tenure-track or permanent positions of the participating departments. Our attendees were six female and two male early career researchers. Moreover, several people from the GARCIA project, belonging both the DISI and the DSRS departments, participated to the event.

The facilitators who led the workshop were:

Bianca Elzenbaumer, PhD in Design from Goldsmiths, University of London. She currently works as research fellow at Leeds College of Art. In her practice-led doctoral thesis she explored precarious working conditions in the cultural industries. Since 2015, together with Fabio Franz, she has been running nomadic Precarity Pilot workshops throughout Europe in order to generate ideas for inventive yet feasible actions against precarization (www.precaritypilot.net).

Fabio Franz is a PhD candidate at the Sheffield School of Architecture. His practice-led research focuses on the role of design in making of commons and community economies. Since 2005, he has been working together with Bianca Elzenbaumer as the Precarity Pilot workshops and at the design research practice Brave New Alps (www.brave-new-alps.com).

Maurizio Teli holds a PhD in Sociology and Social Research from the University of Trento. Then we moved, as postdoc, to the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science of the same university. He is now assistant professor at the Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute. In his research, he investigates the political intersections between the social sciences and the participatory design of digital technologies.

In the workshop with early career researchers, organised in the afternoon, we wanted to use, as starting point, the criteria for the recruitment of assistant professors identified by senior academics in the “Reflexive working group with committee members” realised the same day in the morning (Bozzon et al. 2016). The goal was to use these criteria and put them at play and discussion in relation to the lived experience of early-career researchers. The main purpose was to question and enrich the perspectives produced in the reflexive working group and to propose productive interventions.

Firstly, after an introduction about the GARCIA project and the concept of leaky pipeline, we divided the participants in two groups of 5 people to reflect on and map the conditions of their professional career path. The underlying questions we suggested as possible guidelines of the discussion were:

- What kind of production does your PhD/postdoc position encourage?
- What share of your work do you think is taking you closer to obtain a permanent position in academia?
- What dilemmas do you encounter?

- Do you see differences between the working practices of male and female colleagues?
- What aspects do you see as beyond your control?
- How does looking for achieving the requirements affect your everyday life?

The main purpose was to identify processes and dynamics in their own professional development paths and institution.

Figure 3.2. Picture taken during the workshop

The second activity consisted in working again in the same small groups, this time starting from the summary of the maps elaborated by professors in the reflexive working group with committee members. The main underlying question was:

- From what we have discussed so far, how would you suggest that these aspects should be tweaked, reformulated, dealt with – especially in relation to inclusiveness and wellbeing – in a gender perspective?

With this activity, our goal was – starting from the criteria suggested for the recruitment process pointed out in the morning by professors – to construct a dialogue and to elaborate different alternatives from the perspective of early career researchers, relevant and salient in the field of the STEM, which might have a positive impact on the situation.

The discussion was fluid and extremely participated, in particular because many of the participants, women and men, were already in the process of sending applications, so they had clear in mind all the challenges related to it. Starting from their personal

experiences, especially comparing female and male colleagues, it was discussed how strongly gender influences the academic career of individuals.

As a last activity, the attendees had been asked to discuss all together the outcomes of the group work and to formulate points for the creation of a shared document that could help to develop a better preparation and awareness of candidates for selection procedures. Moreover, the participants collectively elaborated a list of requests related to their everyday working life and to the recruitment process, to be discussed also with professors in the plenary session of the day after.

Figure 3.3. Attendees discussing the posters realised during the workshop

The main purpose of the workshop was spreading awareness of gender practices and how to counter them in the evaluation of excellence in academia. Moreover, we wanted to develop some dissemination guidelines on how to avoid biases in evaluating excellence at university. For these reasons we collectively decided to write the “Manifesto for the future of precarious postdocs and PhD students”, titled “Making Visible”.

Then, the inputs that came out from the workshop were analysed and merged with the outcomes of the committee members working group by the GARCIA team and represented in the manifesto. In addition, it had been decided to graphically re-elaborate the document in order disseminate it among UNITN academic community but also outside our institution.

MAKING VISIBLE

A MANIFESTO
FOR THE FUTURE
OF PRECARIOUS
POST-DOCS AND
PH.D. STUDENTS*

***OUR LIVES AND WORK ARE OFTEN INVISIBLE.
THE RULES OF THE GAME ARE INVISIBLE TOO.
MAKE THEM VISIBLE, MAKE OUR LIVES BETTER.***

- x ***We are not just writing machines. We are gendered bodies, we have friends, lovers, and families. Think about it when you evaluate us.***

- x ***We are asked to be totally available, always. Gender imbalance in the academia is built from the early stages of the scientific path. Don't consider young researchers who also chaise thier personal development unable to meet this criteria.***

- x ***We play the academic game but its rules are opaque. Show us its mechanisms so we can be strategic players.***

- x ***We are required to be excellent. Let us understand the parameters of excellence, who defines them and how.***

- x ***We produce and share knowledge with colleagues around the world. Intellectually encourage, materially support, and institutionally value this.***

* This manifesto emerged from the proposals collected during the "Making Academic Careers Together" workshop, part of the GARCIA project and hosted by the COOP2016 conference. The workshop saw the participation of professors, post-docs, and Ph.D. students attending the conference and/or affiliated to the University of Trento.

We are not just writing machines in Trento

We care for other people, we can have health issues. Officially consider this while evaluating our CVs for different positions or grants. Don't think we should necessarily and often change the city we live in.

We play the academic game in Trento

We are evaluated through logics we cannot see. Tell us what the rules of the game are. Let us understand your politics. Our contracts are short-time. Define the renewal conditions since the beginning.

We are required to be excellent in Trento

Make evaluation criteria explicit. How are publications, teaching, and grants evaluated? Tell us who evaluates us. Make public the names of the committee members at the time of application. When you have evaluated us, help us improve through publicly available reports.

We produce and share knowledge in Trento

Seeking professional development, we attend conferences, co-author with international colleagues and visit universities around the world. Encourage these activities. Grant all of us the time and money to participate in them. Consider this when evaluating us.

We are academics and professionals in Trento

Make all our work visible. Recognise us as Principal Investigators for externally-funded projects. Recognise the work we invest in thesis supervision, independently from our teaching. Recognise the administrative work we do. Value and appreciate the peer-to-peer work we do, for example mentoring younger scholars.

Gendering the Academy
and Research: combating
Career Instability and Asymmetries

Supported by
the 7th Framework Programme
of the European Union

Thus, the outcomes were resubmitted during the dedicated time slot in the final plenary session to discuss about several biases – and in particular gender biases – in the construction of excellence and in the recruitment procedures, showing the manifesto as a merge of the contributions received from both groups (the committee member reflection group and the candidates workshop). This session of restitution was extremely helpful because we had the chance to present the outputs of the two workshops to a larger audience, namely all the COOP participants. Our results had been welcomed with lively interest from the audience, that responded with questions and other very interesting inputs about the topics in the manifesto.

Due to the enthusiastic reaction in the plenary session, we decided to disseminate the manifesto among the UNITN academic community, but also outside our institution, in order to raise awareness among committee members on the gender practices and the problematics related to the access to tenure positions. For this reason, we created a dedicated webpage (<http://www.making-visible.com/>), that is still under construction, but that is already online.

3.2.2 SSH department (DSRS)

In the Department of Sociology and Social Research, the GARCIA project implemented two different kind of activities focussed on how to empower early career researchers, especially female researchers, and how to prepare applications for an assistant professor position. These two actions had been led by professor Barbara Risman, in residence at the University of Trento for a month, in June 2016.

Professor Barbara Risman has been Head of the Department of Sociology at the University of Illinois at Chicago, President-Elect (2014-2015) of the Southern Sociological Society and still Vice-President Elect of the American Sociological Association. After a year fellowship at Stanford she was visiting professor at the Department of Sociology and Social Research in Trento. In addition to the activities realised for the GARCIA project, professor Risman taught an optional course for the master students of the DSRS titled “Introduction to qualitative methods” and gave a seminar in which she presented her new book “Where Will the Millennials Take Us? A Gender Structure Analysis of Identities, Marital Plans and Beyond”.

The activities she led as consultant for the GARCIA project, involving PhD candidates, postdocs and research fellow from the DSRS, took place in different moments:

- The first action was a workshop titled “Professional Development Workshop: Career Planning for Early Career Researchers”. In this occasion, Professor Risman focussed on the practical skills needed by early career researchers for their career development such as cv-writing, preparation of job applications and interview strategies.
- Moreover, we organised individual follow-up colloquia, where PhDs candidates, postdocs and research fellows had the possibility to have one-to-one meetings with her to talk about their specific research projects and receive a personalised counselling for their professional development.

In organising both activities, our main concern was to identify a period over the

academic year not saturated by exams, deadlines and teaching duties in order to guarantee the participation of a consistent number of early career researchers.

The workshop “Professional Development Workshop: Career Planning for Early Career Researchers” took place on June the 13th, 2016 in the Department of Sociology and Social research. The event had been disseminated through different channels: all the postdocs and research fellows of the department had been contacted via email with a formal invitation both by the GARCIA team and the PhD office. Due to their actual small number – seven in 2016, of which four working in the GARCIA project – we decided to open the workshop also to the PhD candidates of the DSRS. The event was also promoted by the department website and the university weekly newsletter.

Figure 3.4. University weekly newsletter

Moreover, posters of the workshop had been affixed in the public display boards of the department.

June 13th, 2016 – h. 14:00

Meeting Room – 3rd Floor, Via Verdi 26 Trento

Professional Development Workshop: Career Planning for Early Career Researchers

presents

Barbara Risman

The seminar is designed for non-tenure researchers. It will be in English.

Professor Risman will focus on the practical skills needed by early career researchers for their career development such as cv-writing, preparation of job applications and interview strategies. Professor Risman will also have **individual follow-up meetings** with some of the participants. These individual advising and counselling appointments will be on the researcher present projects, future applications and more broadly about his/her career development. If interested in booking an individual session, please email francesca.fiore@unitn.it. The number of individual colloquium is limited.

Segreteria Dipartimento - Via Verdi, 26 – 38122 Trento, Italy - Tel. +39 0461/281322, Fax +39 0461/281458 segreteria.ers@unitn.it

Figure 3.5. Poster disseminating the workshop

The attendees of the workshop were five, four female and one male. They all belonged to the DSRS except for one male PhD candidate, from the department of engineering.

The workshop was opened asking the participants to provide a brief introduction about themselves, about the reasons why they were there and what they expected. Then, professor Risman introduced herself and her main theoretical framework for analysing gender as a social structure. Risman's theoretical argument directs attention to three distinct levels of analysis: the individual, the interactional, and the macro, as well as the causal and recursive relationships between them. She wanted to use this structure also in conducting the workshop.

The main aim was to provide early career researchers useful tools for their career development analysing the possible option they could have and maximizing their talents.

She problematized three main topics:

- Gender inequalities, gender biases and stereotypes in academic career development, also related to the personal development.
- (Geographic) mobility as mandatory for the development of an academic career.
- The need to balance research and teaching.

She introduced these topics asking what expectations the participants had for their professional career, if and how much they were ready to move from their home countries to improve their professional skills and if for them it was more important the teaching part or the research one. Depending from the given answers she was providing different strategies.

Her advices can be summarized in 3 main points:

- *Geographical mobility*
Being geographically flexible had been described as a key point for an early career researcher's professional development. In order to develop his/her path and to develop his/her academic network, a researcher will have to move from the own home institution, at least for some time. If someone does not want to move, she said, a career in the academia could be difficult to develop, but it could still be possible to do research. Some alternative options, in fact, could be working for a NGO, for the government, but also in the private market. Moving, on the other hand, involve a large amount of challenges, in particular concerning the balance of work and private life. This is an aspect that needs to be taken into consideration, in particular in regard to family or partners conciliation.
- *Balance between research and teaching activities*
Professor Risman underlined the importance to understand how to balance teaching and research activities. In her opinion, an academic career is developed through the union of these two tasks, one contaminating the other. Despite this, there are opportunities to focus more on teaching activities or more on research one. The private market, indeed, has been presented as a potential option also for people who love doing research but not much teaching. If someone is more passionate about teaching, instead, her advice was to focus also on publishing in specialized issues about teaching and to present a catalogue of research topic you might be capable of providing.
- *The role of mentors*
Large importance has also been given to the role of the mentors, that could help early career researchers in finding their path and developing their talents. Moreover, they could become fundamental stakeholders in building the right network to achieve and maximize possible achievements.

The discussion was fluid and participated, and flowed like a friendly conversation, in which professor Risman was sharing her expertise and was answering the questions of the participants. Her knowledge was based on academic career as a career to be developed at the international level, and she provided a variety of examples and their positionality *vis-à-vis* the gender structure. Due to her research interests, she presented

the data using a gender structure analysis: she was always really careful in keeping a gender perspective when presenting the different options.

Finally, she concluded the talk with her argument that in order to reach a just world with full equality we must construct a post-gender society.

The commitment of all participants was reached during the working group and several participants also signed up for the individual counselling meeting.

The individual follow-up colloquia took place between June the 13th, 2016 and June the 24th, 2016. The PhD candidates, postdocs and research fellows who attended to the workshop, but also other people among their colleagues, had the possibility to have a one-to-one meeting with professor Risman to talk about their specific research projects and receive personalised counselling for their professional development. They had the chance, in fact, to present their research projects and to have personal advices in how to develop them.

The early career researchers had been invited via email, both through formal and informal channels. Moreover, there were posters around the department in order to disseminate this action. The colloquium had been organised with the help of the GARCIA team using a doodle in order to find the perfect match between prof. Risman's availabilities and the candidates'.

Most of the meeting had been done at the DSRS but we also gave the possibility to fix an appointment via Skype for the people who were abroad for research duties. In total nine colloquia had been organised, three of which using Skype. We had four women and five men for the individual counselling. Each colloquium lasted between one and two hours.

The people who did the colloquium had then been reached by the GARCIA team in order to have feedbacks on the counselling through some brief informal questions. All of them were extremely satisfied of the talk they had with professor Risman. They were glad they had this opportunity because it was extremely helpful to have such and expert point of view that could guide them through their doubt on their research project.

3.2.3 University level

At the University level, the GARCIA team collaborated with the Scientific Research and Technological Transfer Division of the University of Trento to the organization of a training course on the ERC Starting Grant 2016 selection procedures conducted by an expert of the Italian Agency for the Promotion of European Research (APRE, <http://www.apre.it/5481>).

In organising the training, our main concern was to foster the adoption of a gender-sensitive approach in the planning and in the implementation of a seminar dedicated to the support of young researchers' career development at the university level. For this reason, we negotiate with the Scientific Research and Technological Transfer Division and with the invited expert of the APRE:

- the inclusion of a caption in the invitation email which explicitly mentioned the adoption of gender-balance criteria in the selection of the participants;
- and the inclusion of a specific focus on gender issues connected to the ERC Starting grant procedures and selection processes among the contents of the workshop.

The training course took place the 29 October 2015 at the Department of Sociology and Social Research. The trainer was Serena Borgna (APRE H2020 NCP European Research Council).

The event had been promoted through a dedicated page on the University website (<http://www.unitn.it/en/ateneo/52487/horizon-2020-european-research-council-erc-starting-grant-2016>). An email invitation was sent by the university administrative offices to all the UNITN scientific community, with specific attention to the early stage researchers of the University of Trento (mainly postdocs and fixed term assistant professors). Moreover, the event was promoted to all the postdocs at the UNITN by the members of the Representative Board of the Postdocs.

The training course was organized in two parts:

- 1) A workshop focused on the modalities of the ERC Starting Grant 2016: eligibility requirements, proposal description and budget, application procedure, and evaluation rules with a specific focus on gender issues connected to all the phases of the submission and evaluation process.
- 2) Individual meetings aimed at offering tailored advices on specific ERC Starting Grant 2016 project proposals.

<p>Programme:</p> <p>8.30- 8.45 Registration (please observe punctuality in order to start presentations in due time)</p> <p>8.45 - 9.00 Welcome (Vanessa Ravagni - Scientific Research and Technological Transfer Division - University of Trento).</p> <p>9.00-12.30 - Modalities of the ERC Starting Grant call 2016: eligibility requirements, proposal description and budget, application procedure, evaluation rules (Serena Borgna - APRE H2020 NCP European Research Council).</p> <p>- Questions and Answers</p> <p>Afterwards:</p> <p>Individual meetings (room 9) upon request (to: citta_research@unitn.it; tel. 1148)</p>
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Figure 3.6. Program of the training course

The access to the individual meetings was subordinated to the submission of a draft of the ERC research proposal in order to received ad-hoc feedbacks and suggestions. Moreover, as explicitly mentioned in the invitation email, gender balance criteria were respected in selecting the participants.

The workshop was attended by 15 early stages researchers (8 female and 7 male), and 4 researchers (2 male + 2 female) participated to the individual meetings.

3.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

This paragraph focuses on the evaluation of the two workshops. More precisely, we will consider the following four points: 1) what have worked when performing the working groups; 2) what challenges and resistances we encountered; 3) what learning points we gain from planning the working groups; 4) the specificity of UNITN context and what future action could be undertaken.

3.3.1 STEM department

During the workshop, the participants were open to discuss all the issues emerged in the conversation, in particular starting from their personal experiences and analysing the context they are into, in particular our institution, the University of Trento. Their perception has been built from their personal experience and the context they knew, but because they all spent some period abroad, they could also make comparisons among different universities. They soon realised, in fact, that the identified dynamics, in particular regarding gender practices, do not differ much from country to country. Nevertheless, they had to admit that, in particular due to the contractual working conditions, the Italian context is more complicated than others in order to grow and make progress in the academic career.

The discussion in the group flowed easily: working in small groups all the participants had the chance to participate and contribute with their inputs and perceptions. The use of tools proper of the collaborative practices also enhanced everyone to interact with the group. Possible elements that helped the good flow of the conversation were the heterogeneity of the participants and having external facilitators of the workshop.

The most challenging moment arrived when the outcomes of the reflexive working group with committee members were analysed.

The main areas of discussion, thus, focussed on:

- The definition of excellence
- Academia as a highly competitive environment
- The invisibility of early career researchers

The input of potential committee members that came out from the working group and translated in action points and recommendations – in order to avoid discriminations and to acknowledge gender differences in the applications (Bozzon et al. 2016) – had been considered as true and reasonable but, at some points, far from the reality of what happened in the selection processes they participated to. For example, committee members said that, as member of a committee for recruiting an assistant professor, in the process they should being aware of the invisibility of part of the activities carried out by early career researchers – especially women – and of the risk to under recognise their work, the difficulty to balance personal life and work, and the importance to acknowledge the pressure of academic requirements. These statements had been underlined as valuable and all true, but far from what is actually evaluated.

For these reasons the idea of the manifesto came up, to disseminate some shared thoughts that could help many other early career researchers to feel recognised, but

also to make the committee members aware of possible discriminations in order to avoid them and to acknowledge gender differences in the applications. Doing so, some possible resistances had been transformed in a positive input in order to create something new and meaningful, the manifesto.

Having the right number of participants for a workshop we had the possibility to focus on the personal experiences but also to abstract from them and deductively move to wider point of views. It gave to the group many fruitful inputs for the dialogue, involving all the participants and keeping their full attention until the end.

Moreover, it was crucial to have a dedicated moment in the plenary session during the last day of the conference planned ahead. In this context – also with the help of the professors who attended the GARCIA workshop and their involvement – in the plenary session we were able to stimulate their colleagues to be involved in a broader discussion. Indeed, in the restitution moment in the plenary session, where we were presenting the results of the workshops, people who participated felt that their personal stories contributed to create the “Manifesto for the future of precarious post-docs and PhD students”, elaborated on the basis of both the workshops realised with committee members and with early career researchers at the DISI and they all endorsed the document.

The goal of the manifesto was to make visible that researchers are people with needs and early career researchers should not be invisible. In particular, we received many positive feedbacks on the work done during that day. All the professors and young researchers who were at the restitution moment asked for more information, in particular about how they could disseminate the manifesto. For this reason, we decided to create a dedicated webpage (<http://making-visible.com/>), in order to maximise the visibility of the contribution elaborated during the workshop and to share it as much as possible.

From the discussions it appeared that the specific point that could be valid for our institution (UNITN), are shared also among many other academic contexts. Our main purpose, which future working group leaders may take into account, is spreading awareness of gender biased and how to counter potential discriminations in the evaluation of excellence. The manifesto and the guidelines emerged from the workshops will be disseminated to enlighten gender biased in evaluating excellence in the university.

3.3.2 SSH department

In the process of organising the working group at the DSRS, the most strategic choice concerned the selection of the external facilitator. In fact, we deliberately decided to entrust the conduction of the workshop to a visiting professor with a wide competence on gender studies and a long and bright career in academia. Due to her expertise and experience she is well-known and valued within the DSRS community and then attractive for early career researchers.

In organising the event, we tried to combine the needs of our facilitator and the commitments of the doctoral school (like midterm deadlines). It was decided to open

the action to PhD students for two reasons: firstly, because it is important to understand how to develop the best strategies in order to build an academic career since the early stages; secondly, because in 2016 the DSRS had only seven postdocs and four of them were already involved in the GARCIA project, so it seemed limiting not to open these events to a larger number of people who could benefit from them.

As a positive result we had the participation to the workshop of four out of seven postdoctoral research fellows of the department and two of them had an individual meeting lately with professor Risman.

Interestingly, while at the workshop took part only female early career researchers of the DSRS (with the exception of a men from the STEM disciplines), the individual colloquia attracted both men and women.

The workshop had the strength of having offered a dynamic model of career building, and it showed how to be strategic in the career planning. Moreover, part of the facilitator attention was dedicated to make sure to capitalize on the work young researchers do, but also following their research interests. She offered a wide perspective on both the United States and the European contexts.

Even if her vision and advices on professional development were not related to national borders, a potential limit of the presentation was the lack of specific knowledge and experience of the facilitator on the Italian context. At the same time, she incited all the participants to project their career development in an international horizon without national borders.

Other than this, both the workshop and the colloquia had been appreciated by the attendees and highly evaluated. They did not stimulate much discussion but, from the participants' feedbacks, they provided many useful tips in order to develop the individual specific research projects and career paths.

3.3.3 University level

The Scientific Research and Technological Transfer Division organizes every year several training courses to support the participation of (early stages) researchers to selections both at the Italian and European level in order to obtain research funding.

The contribution of the GARCIA Project to the organization of a training course on the ERC Starting Grant selection procedures dedicated to early stages researchers fostered the adoption of a gender-sensitive approach in organising and conducting such kind of events. On one hand, a peculiar attention was given to the participation of female postdocs to the activities offered during the training course by the adoption of gender-balance criteria. On the other hand, the development of a specific focus on gender issues among the topics developed during the workshop allowed to raise the preparation and the awareness of (women) candidates on unfair dynamics often hidden in selection procedures.

3.4 CONCLUSION

In organising the activities with early career researchers in the two GARCIA beneficiary departments at the UNITN, we followed two completely different strategies which led to different outcomes.

In both departments, the implemented activities created an open space to reflect upon the processes that foster the reproduction of gender asymmetries in academia as well as the strategies that should allow early career researchers to develop a successful career and obtain a stable academic position.

In the case of the DISI, we chose three facilitators with a previous experience in conducting reflexive working groups in STEM environments, and with competences in gender and precariousness. Moreover, we decided to organise the workshop within the international framework of the COOP conference and to create a situation where both early career researchers and professors could share opinions and points of view on career development and recruitment criteria in academia. Given the high turnover of postdocs and their limited chances of obtaining a tenured position within the DISI (and more in general in the Italian context), it is crucial to maintain an international horizon in raising awareness on gender bias in career development.

We reached a strong commitment among the participants during the workshop. The thoughts and experiences of the early career researchers contributed to the contents included in the manifesto presented in the plenary session of the COOP conference. This document was shared after the conference at the UNITN and at the international level through a dedicated website.

In the case of the DSRS, our main concern was to offer to the postdocs and PhD students of the department the possibility to discuss about career development strategies in academia with an appraised female expert with an international experience, a prestigious position within the scientific community, and a gender sensitive approach. In such context, both the workshop and the individual colloquia carried out by Barbara Risman with early career researchers of the DSRS offered an unconventional discussion on how to play the academic game, and more specifically on gender differences in academic careers, unhooked by the provincialism which characterised the Italian and local debate. Moreover, the individual colloquia were particularly appreciated by the participants because they had the chance to obtain fruitful and unexpected advices on their career strategies.

In the case of the training course on the ERC Starting Grant, we tried to overcome the boundaries of the events organized at the department level, raising awareness on gender asymmetries hidden in academic selection processes also in the UNITN scientific community.

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4. THE NETHERLANDS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of this report is to describe and reflect on the execution of WP7 task 7.4 “Workshops for prospective candidates”. The report consists of two parts: the set-up and the evaluation of the workshops. The accumulation of reports from all GARCIA beneficiaries will be used to build a tool for universities and research institutes to bring awareness to early career researchers on the construction of excellence and the practice of appointment procedures of early career academics (Deliverable 7.4: Format tool reflexive working groups).

The goal of the GARCIA workshops we conducted was to inform early career researchers (ECRs) in the IMR and the IMAPP about the criteria for building an academic career. The first aim was to show both the ‘formal’ criteria often displayed in job advertisement texts, as opposed to the actual criteria deployed when a candidate is selected. The message was: don’t be scared away by the ‘excellence’ criteria in a job advertisement as not all criteria are equally important and committees are more lenient towards requirements than assumed. The second aim was to bring an understanding as to how gender plays or might play a role in the recruitment and selection processes for the positions ECRs (may) aspire to gain someday. For instance, candidates are often judged on their teaching evaluations, but research has shown that women are evaluated worse than men. This may well have gendered implications for their appointment. Additionally, the third aim was to emphasize and explicate the role of visibility and informal networks in the building of an academic career.

We conducted two workshops, one in each institute, i.e. IMR and IMAPP. The target groups were PhD candidates and postdocs. The two workshops were planned shortly after each other, on Monday 11 April 2016 (IMR) and Tuesday 12 April 2016 (IMAPP). They were organized in consultation with the secretaries of both institutes regarding practical arrangements. Invitations were written by one of the GARCIA researchers and then sent out to the PhD candidates through the doctoral officer and to the postdocs by one of the GARCIA researchers (IMR) and by the secretaries (IMAPP).

The Radboud University is active in organizing workshops and courses for its increasing pool of PhD candidates. For the postdocs less courses are organized, though the university HR department is currently developing a curriculum for this specific target group (temporarily employed academic staff) in consultation with the TRAP network, a network for temporarily employed academic personnel such as postdocs. Courses are aimed at building academic skills (e.g., presenting research, writing skills) or on broader career orientation (e.g., ‘what makes you tick?’), yet a specific workshop or course on the norms and criteria in academia does not exist. This is similar for the IMR: no courses or workshops similar to the GARCIA workshop are organized.

4.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

4.2.1 SSH department (IMR)

Ten IMR PhD candidates and one IMR postdoc registered for the workshop of 11 April, among which nine women and two men. Two PhD candidates (both women) cancelled before the start of the workshop. Five female PhD candidates from the Institute for Gender Studies also participated. In total, thirteen PhD candidates and one postdoc participated, among which two men and twelve women, 14 in total.

The workshop was set up as follows. First, Marieke van den Brink introduced the team. Channah introduced the GARCIA project. A quick introductory round was made for the participants to get to know each other and for Marieke and Channah to make an inventory of what each participant wanted to learn or discuss during the workshop. The topics IMR participants mentioned were:

- Generally: curious about results GARCIA and what is needed to pursue an academic career.
- Applying for a postdoc grant or position: what steps to take? Going abroad?
- How to enhance chances to stay in academia?
- How to become an assistant professor?
- Stay in or leave academia?
- “What is ‘excellence’? Would I be eligible for such label?”
- Gender practices.

Channah Herschberg then presented the results of WP7.1. She showed an example of an extreme case’ job advertisement for an assistant professorship and went through the criteria mentioned. She then explained that our results show that committee members do not give the same priority to all criteria, and that research is the most decisive criterion for early career scholars. The question came up whether doing a postdoc is a necessary/wise thing to do. Laura explained her view based on interviews from the GARCIA project. After that Marieke took over by introducing gender into the discussion. She also pointed out the role of informal networks in academic recruiting and career building. After a short break, a discussion was held between the workshop holders and participants: the latter were given time to ask questions about what they had heard and things they wanted to know. We finished the workshop with handing out an evaluation form, which asked:

- *What are the most important insights you gained from the workshop?*
- *How did you experience the presentation and facilitation of the workshop? (Pleasant unpleasant, informal, formal, informative, etc.)*
- *What could be improved about the workshop?*

We discuss the answers to these questions under 3. *Evaluation of the task.*

Plenty of questions (Q) were asked and remarks (R) were made during the workshop:

- Q: Response to ideal criteria: cringing. “Is this for a full professor or an assistant?” (cynical)

- Q: Does a PhD need to be finished when you apply for an assistant professorship?
- Q: How is quality of publications defined?
- Q: Do you know beforehand who are in the selection committee?
- Q: What is a pipeline (of publications)? And how to show your pipeline in your CV?
- Q: Can a 'research line' also be in another topic than your PhD?
- Q: Is a teaching qualification necessary before you apply?
- Q: How do you show you have an international network?
- Q: Does a committee look at the quality of your PhD in respect to the time you took to finish?
- Q: Why are there so few postdocs at the IMR?
- R: Doubt about whether a European project postdoc is good for your research track record, as many reports need to be written and actual paper writing does not happen until late in the project.
- Q: How common is it to apply for a postdoc that is not exactly in your field? Especially difficult with gender studies research.
- R: Danger of many short term contracts. Always apply for multiple grants.
- Q: When should you apply for grants? Already during your PhD?
- Q: Can you apply at a university where no one knows you and vice versa?
- R: Peer support: brag about your PhD colleagues!
- Q: Should you tell your supervisors about your doubts and insecurities?
- Q: Would part-time work be possible?

4.2.2 STEM department (IMAPP)

Eight people registered for the workshop of 12 April, among which six women and two men. In total, two PhD candidates and six postdocs actually participated, among which three men and five women. One woman cancelled, and one man showed up without registering.

The workshop was set up as follows. First, Marieke van den Brink introduced both the GARCIA team and the workshop agenda. Then Channah introduced the GARCIA project. A quick introductory round was made for the participants to know each other and for Marieke and Channah to make an inventory of what each participant wanted to learn or discuss during the workshop. The topics IMAPP participants mentioned were:

- Expectations of committee members when you apply? How to apply?
- What to put in your CV and what not?
- What steps to take to become postdoc and build an academic career?
- Other point of view on the topic of academic careers.
- What is a good tenure track-eligible profile?
- How to build an academic network
- Orienting on academic careers

Channah Herschberg then presented the results of WP7.1. She showed an example of a job advertisement for a tenure track assistant professorship and went through the criteria mentioned. She then explained how committee members do not give the same priority to all criteria, and that research is the most decisive criterion for

early career scholars. After that Marieke took over by explaining gender practices in recruitment and selection. She also pointed out the role of informal networks in academic recruiting and career building. After a short break, a discussion was held between the workshop facilitators and participants: the latter were given time to ask questions about what they had heard and things they wanted to know. We finished the workshop with handing out an evaluation form, which asked

- *What are the most important insights you gained from the workshop?*
- *How did you experience the presentation and facilitation of the workshop? (Pleasant unpleasant, informal, formal, informative, etc.)*
- *What could be improved about the workshop?*

We discuss the answers to these questions under 3. *Evaluation of the task.*

Again, plenty of questions (Q) were asked and remarks (R) were made during the workshop:

- R: The list of criteria in a job advertisement seem “tough”. Most tough are: clear vision on research line; external funding; teaching in Dutch (foreigners); teaching
- How is independent research evaluated by a selection committee?
- Is a postdoc necessary? To show independent research?
- How important is originality?
- R: Quality over quantity concerning publications. But that’s weird in an institute where PhD candidates need to have five papers published.
- Q: Is the H-index important?
- R: FOM (national institute) does not give you postdoc money if you have done a PhD in the Netherlands
- Q: Why is doing a postdoc abroad necessary?
- Q: Why is going abroad supposedly more difficult for women?
- R: Own research line: even if you’re not doing your own research you can become the leader of a research project.
- Q: Does a committee want to see specialization or generalization?
- Q: Does a fellowship count as external funding? Or gaining data through proposals?
- R: External funding in reality is the most important criterion.
- R: The double bind for women is recognized, mostly by the women in the room. (Men are silent or unaware).
- Q: Does it help to have women in a committee or are they also biased?
- Q: Is it about being lucky when it comes to the committee and your chances to be hired?
- Q: Informal recruitment: what if your supervisor does not support you? How to overcome this?
- Q: Are recommendations from supervisors relevant or not?
- Q: How important are grants for getting a tenure track position?
- Q: Concerning the two body problem: should you tell a committee about this beforehand?

4.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

4.3.1 SSH department

What worked for you when planning and performing the workshops?

The secretaries were helpful in arranging a room and the lunch, which alleviated some of the work. It proved helpful to have the doctoral officer of the IMR send around invitations. This sparked enough interest from PhD candidates. The officer sent around a reminder which led to more registrations. Laura Berger sent around the invitation to the few postdocs of the IMR.

What challenges and resistances have you come across when planning and performing the workshops? How did you overcome them (or not)?

We did not come across any challenges when planning the workshop. Being pro-active and arranging a room well in advance helped to secure these organizational aspects. The good contact with the secretaries helped. When performing the workshop the only challenge was the time management, as the audience raised many questions. Because many questions and issues were discussed during the more formal part of the workshop, not much time was left at the end for discussion.

What are the learning points you gained from planning and performing the workshops?

- Start well in advance with arranging organizational stuff: room, lunch
- Have an intermediary send around the invitations: in this case the doctoral officer, who has a list of the target group
- Prepare the PowerPoint together with all workshop holders
- Keep the time schedule in mind but be flexible. Make sure there is enough room for questions and remarks. Do not tell at the start of the workshop that there is room at the end to raise questions but incorporate time for questions during the presentation of the research results.
- Make clear that the purpose of the workshop is to present our research findings in the particular department, not absolute do's and don'ts. Point to people's own agency to change their situation and/or the university system.
- The participants showed an interest in more practical aspects such as: how to write a CV, and how to overcome gender bias in recruitment and selection. This is something to take into account in the workshop development.
- Be aware of the 'tone of voice' when you discuss gender consequences of academic practices such as recruitment and selection. It is important that early career academics know about gender in academia, but they should not be discouraged too much.

What feedback did you get from participants?

Taken together, the participants gave the following answers on the evaluation form.

- *What are the most important insights you gained from the workshop?*
 - Insight in criteria and considerations by selection committees
 - The importance of visibility and informal networking; importance of a "champion" who supports and sponsors you

- What is important in choosing for either postdoc or assistant professor position and advantages/disadvantages of both positions
- Gender biases women can come across
- The importance of building your own research line or at least have a story of what you plan to do research-wise
- The fact that not all criteria are evenly important for committees
- Informal recruitment strategies
- Importance of “in pipeline” publications
- Knowing what is important to pursue an academic career; criteria for assistant professorship; research is prioritized over teaching and career outside academia
- *How did you experience the presentation and facilitation of the workshop?*
 - Open atmosphere
 - Informative
 - Room for discussion and questions
 - Feeling of confidentiality
- *What could be improved about the workshop?*
 - Generally: more time for discussion. In the end not a lot of time was available for further questions.
 - The workshop gave evidence as to gender biases in recruitment, but participants would have liked to discuss more regarding what they could do to overcome obstacles? How to increase their chances?
 - Some practical examples and for instance the discussing of a concrete case of an appointment procedure would have been nice.
 - How to translate criteria into your CV? What are necessary competences and how to write them down.
 - Registration process was a little confusing (different names involved).

What was specific for your context, which future workshop leaders need to take into account?

- Criteria are different in different fields. Attune your story according to those differences; don't make it a general story. Postdoc experience, for instance, is not a common criterion within the IMR. This is why the question on whether to choose a postdoc or assistant professor position came up.
- The IMR has a big group of gender researchers, so that even none-gender-related researchers have some knowledge of gender. This helps in the acceptance of the workshops. In other faculties/universities, this might be different.

4.3.2 STEM department

What worked for you when planning and performing the workshops?

The contact with the secretaries was very constructive. As we as organizers are not part of the IMAPP, the secretaries were helpful in arranging a room and the lunch, which

alleviated some of our work. It was not entirely clear how people would be invited. In the end, it was done through a contact of Laura Berger at the IMAPP (a postdoc) who then in the end sent the invitation to the secretaries, who sent it around to the target group. This process led to little insight in which PhD candidates and postdocs were actually invited.

What challenges and resistances have you come across when planning and performing the workshops? How did you overcome them (or not)?

We did not come across any challenges when planning the workshop. Being pro-active and arranging a room well in advance helped to secure these organizational aspects. The good contact with the secretaries helped. When performing the workshop one challenge was the projector that did not work. A secretary called IT support, which helped out. Another challenge was the lack of 'insider knowledge' of the workshop facilitators with regard to the IMAPP disciplines. Some questions that were raised were hard to answer when they were out of the scope of the results of WP7.

What are the learning points you gained from planning and performing the workshops?

- Start well in advance with arranging organizational stuff: room, lunch, etc.
- Have an intermediary send around the invitations, in this case the secretaries, who have a list of the target group.
- Prepare the PowerPoint together with all workshop holders
- Be sure to be in time in the room to have potential bugs fixed in time (e.g., when a projector does not work)
- Keep the time schedule in mind but be flexible. Make sure there is enough room for questions and remarks. Do not tell at the start of the workshop that there is room at the end to raise questions but incorporate time for questions during the presentation of the research results.
- Make clear that the purpose of the workshop is to present our research findings in the particular department, not absolute do's and don'ts. Point to people's own agency to change their situation or the university system.
- The participants showed an interest in more practical aspects such as: how to write a CV, and how to overcome gender bias in recruitment and selection. This is something to take into account in the workshop development.

What feedback did you get from participants?

- *What are the most important insights you gained from the workshop?*
 - Learning what committee members look for when applying for tenure track positions; Information about recruitment and selection criteria is impressive and helpful
 - Requirements for an academic (tenure track) positions are multiple, possible difficult to have at the same time
 - Importance of informal networking
 - There is not one way to have an academic career
 - It is also a matter of luck
 - Building your own 'research line' will be really important
 - Role of personal likability

- *How did you experience the presentation and facilitation of the workshop? (Pleasant unpleasant, informal, formal, informative, etc.)*
 - Pleasant
 - Approachable people
 - Informative
 - Well-organized
 - Room for discussion and own topics
- *What could be improved about the workshop?*
 - More time for discussion. The workshop should be an hour or even 1,5 hours longer to facilitate this. (Multiple respondents)
 - More information and statistics.
 - The popularity: more people should know about the workshop, as it could be important for them as well.
 - A lot of 'what to be done' is discussed, I wish there were a bit on 'how to do' too.

What was specific for your context, which future workshop leaders need to take into account?

- As in the IMAPP, careers are built a bit different for the various sub-fields. You can prepare a general story, but attune your story according to those differences. Being first author on papers, for instance, is not a common criterion within astrophysics. This is why the question on whether that is an objective measure of independent research came up.
- As the pool of PhD candidates and postdoc researchers can consist of researchers who differ considerably with regard to years of experience (e.g., beginning PhD candidates versus postdoc with four years postdoc experience) this should be taken into account when developing the workshop. Spend sufficient time to the recruitment of postdoc positions.

4.4 CONCLUSION

Compare the set-up and evaluation of the workshops in the two departments. What similarities and what differences did you encounter?

The workshop was developed to be interactive with enough time for participants to raise questions, discuss pressing matters, and learn from each other. We succeeded in making this workshop an interactive endeavour.

- Interactive atmosphere: in both departments the participants needed little encouragement to ask their questions or make comments.
- Time shortage: 1,5 hours is probably not very feasible if you also want to have room at the end to discuss questions and issues; providing room for discussion and questions during the presentation of the findings might prove more feasible.
- Practical guidance needed: in both workshops the participants would have liked to see more practical discussion of how to achieve criteria and how to cope with gender bias.

To what extent do you see the workshops as a feasible instrument to create or increase gender awareness among early career researchers?

It proved a very feasible instrument. Both facilitators and participants considered it a quick and low-key way to share insights, and in a way that is familiar to academics. The workshop would probably be even more helpful if there was more time to discuss ways to cope with biases and how to overcome obstacles; but also to give more practical advice on how to be able to achieve the requirements and how to present yourself.

4.5 APPENDICES

Text invitation early career scholars

Dear early career academics,

The [department] is participating in the FP7 GARCIA project (www.garciaproject.eu), which is concerned with the implementation of actions to enhance early career academics' work environment and prospects and promote gender equality in academia.

We would like to invite you, (senior) PhD candidates and postdocs of the institute, to take part in a GARCIA workshop on

building an academic career and the criteria and requirements for early career scholars in the current academic system.

A few of the questions to be discussed are:

- What do selection committees look for?
- How do you build a CV?
- How can you present yourself in such a way that you make an 'excellent' candidate?
- How does gender play a role in recruitment processes?

In the workshop [workshop facilitators] will present the findings of their research and facilitate a discussion about being an early career academic. This workshop will be valuable for preparing yourself for the academic labor market and for planning your career.

The workshop will take place on **[date] in [room]**. Lunch will be provided. Please register with [MAIL] before **[date two weeks prior to workshop]**. Both women and men are invited to join! The registration is on a first come, first serve basis. There is room for fifteen participants.

5. SLOVENIA

5.1 INTRODUCTION

Besides problematizing gender in academia, one of the main goals of the workshop was to discuss the current problem of young scientists in Slovenia.

The bad situation for researchers at the beginning of the academic carrier worsened after the social and economic crises in 2008 and related reforms, as the Government drastically cut down the financial resources for research and teaching. Because of that, it is very hard to obtain national research projects in Slovenia and struggles to get international projects and meet international scientific criteria have become the main focus of many younger scientists. Younger scientists are more or less temporary employed only for the duration of the projects and in many institutions they have become a tool for preparing projects and earning money. Therefore, they hardly find time for in-depth research and writing articles for international publications with a high factor of impact. However, according to the interviews conducted in WP4 and WP7, most of them are without the skills required to achieve academic excellence and to survive in the scientific environment after completing their PhD studies.

Some reasons for their problems originate from the lack of mentoring programmes. Those researchers who reported a bad mentorship were 'left to themselves' (no leadership, advice, task definition, support, regular discussions, exchange of views, orientation regarding how and what to do), or had poor or hierarchical communication with their mentors. In addition, their mentors did not integrate them into the project and article writing, but they allowed them to attend conferences and spend some time abroad (mobility). Some of the researchers were promised a continuing academic career during their PhD studies, but after they completed their PhD, the information about terminating their contracts was sudden and without any detailed explanation.

Furthermore, it also needs to be highlighted that younger scientists from the Institute of the Slovenian Language, which is a test unit within ZRC SAZU (SSH institution), face the problem that they are not forced to be active in preparing project applications, going abroad or attending scientific mobility. As their primary work is to prepare dictionaries or linguistic atlases in desirable time and to educate themselves on these specific issues, which has a long tradition in the linguistic institution, they can work on their scientific criteria (publishing, networking, and attending scientific conferences) only in their free time. Since young female researchers with small children do not have a lot of free time, they are not competitive in the scientific environment and, consequently, less ambitious to be excellent as well. Although the younger scientists at the institution are aware of the situation in other institutions where younger scientists are leaving the academia or moving away from ZRC SAZU because of financial problems and the inability to get new projects, they are not problematising their situation and uncompetitive merits.

However, problems of young scientist in Slovenia are also a consequence of other factors. Higher education in Slovenia has already entered into a phase of mass education. One of the most distinctive characteristics of these developments is the rather high share (60%) of female students among all university students. However, the

presence of female students is not evenly distributed throughout different SSH/STEM scientific fields. As statistical data for the whole country shows, female students greatly outnumber male students in SSH fields at all study levels, particularly in education, health and humanities, while males strongly outnumber their female colleagues in engineering, manufacturing and construction. An exception is the field of agriculture, which is gradually but surely exposed to feminisation among BSc, MSc and particularly PhD students. This general gender imbalance typical for the student population is further reinforced among the research and teaching staff, women being at a disadvantage. Namely, the statistical data demonstrates that universities and research institutions in all scientific fields, except in humanities and medical sciences, and lately also in agriculture, employ more men than women. This is further corroborated with statistical survey data on PhD holders' careers, which is outlined as a scissor-shaped curve, by clearly demonstrating unequal professional trajectories of women and men in science. In typical academic careers, the share of women is decreasing with each higher step on the academic ladder. Moreover, the disadvantaged position of highly educated females is mirrored in statistical data showing that women significantly prevail among the researchers employed with temporary contracts. Therefore, on a general level, statistical indicators and statistical survey data unambiguously demonstrated the existence of a leaky pipeline phenomenon in science in Slovenia.

From the WP5.1 Report, in both test unit departments (ZRC SAZU and Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana – STEM institution), irrespective of their numerical representation, women still to a much lesser extent occupy the important decision making positions in their organisations than their male colleagues, which puts them in a disadvantaged position. The observations, based on statistical data, that university and research departments are still strongly determined by a specific masculine academic culture is further corroborated with the findings of other surveys on PhD holders.

How many workshops did you perform at the GARCIA institute?

During the GARCIA project, we prepared two workshops for Researchers at the beginning of the scientific careers. One was organised in February 2015 and was dedicated to writing a successful application for the Marie Skłodowska-Curie fellowship for Young Researchers. Dean Vuletič, PhD, (fellowship holder from the University of Vienna) and Majda Černič Istenič, PhD, reviewer in the Marie Skłodowska-Curie fellowship shared their experiences. Seventeen researchers from the SSH test department attended the events. Another workshop was organised in the framework of WP7, where the lecture were given by a foreign lecturer Dr. Muriel E Swijghuisen Reigersberg. She is an ethnomusicologist, a Research Development and Policy Manager and a Visiting Fellow at the Music, Mind and Brain research centre, Psychology Department, Goldsmiths, University of London. Her managerial role includes collaborating on open access and data initiatives, ethics and integrity management, medical ethnomusicology and impact, performance studies, research ethics, and the relationship between music, health and wellbeing. From 2012 to 2015, she was a Visiting Research Fellow at the Department of Psychology, Goldsmiths. From 2012, she is working as the Head of Office at the Research Development Department at the Goldsmiths Research Office (University of London). Since she is working in the field of the research

development policy in Goldsmith and—as a researcher, represents an administrative person and a person who is involved in research—she is also competent for explaining the tools for becoming a more successful researcher.

Because young scientists are facing similar problems at SSH and STEM, the prepared workshop was meant for both groups. However, no one from the Biotechnical Faculty (Test unit from STEM discipline) participated.

Explanation of the specific context of the Institute and the departments, e.g. whether similar workshops already exist at your institute.

Several workshops, seminars and lectures were performed at the ZRC SAZU in the past, by the office for administrative support for the application of European projects. Last year special workshop for preparing Horizon 2020 project was performed by international company. Due to the high level of the interest, those workshops had to be continuously performed.

The majority of participants at the workshops were in general young researchers and postdoctoral researches who already successfully and excellently completed the Young Researcher programme (a special position for young people to obtain a PhD financed by the Slovenian Research Agency) and thereby gained an opportunity to continue their research work at the institution. However, the acceptance of researchers depends on the financial capabilities of the institute, which, unfortunately, is increasingly insecure.

To explain the specific context of the Institute and the departments, it is also worth to point out that since Slovenia is a small country. This fact can sometimes be an obstacle, because Slovenia does not have well-known or important institutions with a good administrative support that other, bigger countries have. Ministers in the government do not have enough authority due to their unsteady positions to convince the Minister of Finance to raise the level of quality in this field. In addition, in the last few years, the budget for science in Slovenia decreased by 25%. Consequently, there is no sufficient space for manoeuvring in the Slovenian scientific sphere, even for the decision makers within their research agency. Therefore, especially young academics are forced to work on several projects simultaneously because of the low finances involved.

5.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

Who participated in the workshop?

Invitations for the workshop were sent to all ZRC SAZU institutes and the Biotechnical Faculty ten days before the meeting took place. Participation was obligatory for young researchers from ZRC SAZU as requested by the Director. Participants of the workshop came from different institutes of ZRC SAZU. There were two participants from the Institute of Philosophy, one from the Sociomedical Institute, two from the Jovan Hadži Institute of Biology, one participant from the Slovenian Migration Institute, five from the Anton Melik Geographical Institute, one from the Institute of Ethnomusicology, two from the Institute of Archaeology and three other participants – altogether 17 participants. Out of 21 participants (Director of ZRC SAZU, who was actively involved in

the discussion, and three members of the GARCIA team included), there were 11 women and 10 men.

How did you set up the workshop? What did you present and what questions did you ask? Did you use a specific form of group discussion to disseminate the results and encourage interpersonal learning and discussions?

The initial plan was to set up workshop in which all young academics of the ZRC SAZU institutes and the Biotechnical Faculty would be participating, but in the end, only young academics from the ZRC SAZU institutes participated and three others who did not come from any institute. In the beginning, the Director of ZRC SAZU welcomed the participants and highlighted the importance of the workshop. The participants actively participated in the discussion. The foreign lecturer with several years of experience presented main points in detail while following her PowerPoint.

After the introduction, the lecturer presented the notion of ‘scientific excellence’ and the criteria for its measurement, and asked the participants about the challenges they face in their academic career. She pointed out that today it is expected from researchers to be a ‘Jack-of-all-trades’ while being good at everything they do. Nowadays, the situation is very different from twenty years ago, because researchers have to be able to do everything. They have to be a good writer, a great administrator and a good promoter of themselves. They have to be able to understand the legislation and politics, to be familiar with technologies and to be able to apply for grants. In addition, they have to be good at generating impact, engaging with the public, be open to the media, write good books and combine everything with their teaching responsibilities. Therefore, a huge pressure lies on academics and researchers of today, which needs to be acknowledged. There is also a generational gap between senior and young academics, which are under a huge pressure due to their unstable positions.

The lecturer pointed out that research excellence is not really an objective fact. Colleagues all have a role to play in assessing it. In addition, peer review is not perfect, because there are many interpersonal issues you need to take into consideration. If your field of research is very small, there is a big chance you will probably know who your reviewer is. While talking about measuring excellence, the metrics (the number of citations) is also an imperfect system. Scientists in the arts and humanities field are in a disadvantaged position because the number of citations is the only measurement of their excellence. However, if you are an established scholar, you benefit from your reputation and some institutional support. For example, if you are at the beginning of your career, someone who still has to build a reputation, not many people will cite you. The lecturer suggested that it is necessary to find new measurements for measuring scientific excellence, and presented publishing in open access as a contemporary solution.

Due to the small number of participants, we did not completely follow the suggested plan of the workshop and stick strictly to the gender issue. While leading the workshop, the lecturer focused on the specific Slovenian situation in constructing scientific excellence, research development and the gained experiences. The lecturer also compared the situation in Slovenia with the situation in the UK and advised on how to resolve the current Slovenian situation by taking into account suggestions based on the

UK experience. The lecturer focused on two current problems in science – the problem of scientific excellence and the problem of research practices.

What aspects were most discussed/most popular? Shortly discuss these.

The lecturer advised the participants to engage into policy revisions and pointed out the meaning of the administrative support of the institute. The lecturer, who cooperates in research development at the Goldsmith University, specialising in arts, humanities and social sciences, suggested that we needed to find out what kind of administration we need in Slovenia and if researchers want to cooperate in an administrative support team.

While evaluating the workshop, one of the participants pointed out to the new perspective, which was revealed to him by the information of importance on international networking. The participants also expressed the wish to perform more specific workshops with a certain topic: for example, how to write a project application, how to network, etc. The lecturer dedicated special attention to discuss about what researchers in the beginning or in the middle of their scientific careers can do. She also gave advice on how to be more successful with project applications for funding (grants, scholarships, etc.).

Based on examples from the UK, the lecturer presented ideas on how to face different challenges. This served as useful information to be applied to the Slovenian problems in the scientific sphere. She advised the young academics to use the internet, which offers new ways of engaging, to publish open access (Electronic Depository, the Research Gate, Academia.edu profiles, Twitter) to increase their citation ratings, to engage into policy revisions. In her opinion, to find new work opportunities, they need to be proactive by sending out the information about themselves, sign up to newsletters... The lecturer pointed out that they need to be strategically informed, to attend conferences, etc. To sum it up, they need to get the track record, connections and make a strategic plan of applying for projects and scholarships in order to survive as an academic. She also advised them to attend conferences and to network with their colleagues. In addition, it is useful for them to read the guidance of a project or a grant and make sure that they are eligible to apply, to ask themselves if they have published enough to apply, if they have the time required to apply and if their project is right for the strategic interest of the funder. She also advised the participant to get a letter of support from a company.

The lecturer pointed out that being an early career researcher is a broad definition and that we can be at this stage for many years. She pointed out the importance of having the opportunity to do postdoctoral research, experiences with gaining financial resources (grants), especially today when there are fewer job opportunities available and not many permanent job positions. It is hard to get a permanent job without getting a continuous funding. She presented the knowledge economy in the UK government and diversifying opportunities in education. Due to a higher number of people with a PhD, more people are working as a workforce in the research field, which is why it is harder for them to stay in academia.

The lecturer talked about an increase of numerical measurement of research excellence. She asked the participants: “What is research excellence and who defines it?” They all agreed that the number of citations could not be the only measurement. The participants said it was important to produce and share your results. One of the participants pointed out that the criteria for scientific excellence could be also to discover something new, to create new knowledge, even if not applied at the moment, which can be useful for decades to come. The lecturer asked the audience if publishing in a high-ranking journal could be a criterion for scientific excellence and why this does (not) work well. The participants replied that it represented a more objective measurement, while adding that it is not completely objective, because it depends on the people, who are reading publications and make certain judgements. One of the participants pointed out that it was a good thing, because senior researchers know the field better than you do and they can tell you if your topic is not really new, in case someone else was doing the research already. On the other hand, it is not a good thing if other people read your work, because people envy you. One of the participants pointed out that you could have an argument with a person who might be reviewing you; therefore, it is not really an objective measurement. The problem with the number of citations as a scientific measurement is that you can pick out the people you know, cite them and they cite you back (the usage of a citation network). In addition, your paper can be cited highly even if you are completely wrong. One of the participants pointed out that this is also an evaluation from a much greater pool of researchers; therefore, if they cite you, they give you a conformation that you did a good job.

The lecturer pointed out the construction of the scientific excellence, which is never an objective fact. In terms of the basic fact, certain things were dismissed and certain things were agreed upon. After a while, certain quotations became common knowledge and you stop citing. Besides, scientific excellence is limited by resources and equipment at the institute; therefore, it is newer an objective fact, but determined by the society. The lecturer talked about the impact and asked the participants: “How your research might be useful to the people outside of the academy – long and short term?” She added that if someone visits your website, how you would know this is an impact. It is really what people do after they visit your website with your information. Also, how to measure an impact of a book? You have to introduce the book, talk to people about it, the lecturer added. One of the participants in the audience asked the lecturer: “How does it look like if you get one application declined, but you accept the remarks and improve it – how does it show that you have send it over and over?” The lecturer replied that successful applicants have done exactly that, if criteria says that you can re-apply, you should do it.

What aspects were least discussed/least popular? Shortly discuss these.

Because we are currently facing basic problems in Slovenia in connection with how to achieve scientific excellence—the conditions for achieving scientific excellence are insufficient—we paid a bit less attention to the gender issue itself. We focused our interest on the understanding of gender through other perspectives (finances/grants, networking, and administrative support) in the Slovenian academic sphere. According to the interviews for the 7.2 report, the biggest problems in Slovenia are the general conditions, which the agency defined for gaining projects and grants. Because Slovenia is

currently facing this kind of issues, the problem of gender is of secondary importance. According to the feedback of the workshop, we can conclude that a commitment to use these action points and recommendations does exist among key players. The Director of ZRC SAZU participated in the workshop and in the end, he promised that similar workshops would be held each year. In addition, the young academics of the ZRC SAZU institutes (and a few others) showed an interest in further workshops with similar topics.

5.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

What worked for you when planning and performing the workshop?

While we were planning and performing the workshop, we realised that the huge privilege of our research team is the fact that the Director was part of our team, because this way he was actively helping us to perform workshops. Nevertheless, he was the one who called the ZRC SAZU institutes and young researchers to participate at the workshop. Due to a lack of this kind of support at the Biological Faculty, we were less successful in inviting prospective candidates and persuading them to cooperate in the workshop.

The content of the workshop was focused on problems that ZRC SAZU and the wider Slovenian scientific sphere is currently facing;; therefore, besides problematising gender in academia, we dedicated a lot of attention to the general notion of scientific excellence and unstable positions for young academics in Slovenia. However, this does not mean that Slovenia is not facing the problem of gender inequality.

What challenges and resistances have you come across when planning and performing the workshop? How did you overcome them (or not)?

The main challenge and resistance that we came across when planning and performing the workshop was that the Biological Faculty did not respond to the invitation. We were not able to overcome this challenge. We suggest that it would be wise to rethink whom to invite as a lecturer in the working team to be able to perform successful workshops and disseminations in the future.

What are the learning points you gained from planning and performing the workshop?

One of the learning points we would like to describe is that it is very important that directors are part of the group in a workshop due to their charisma, power and influence to persuade people. In addition, it would be also important to include the Heads of the Institutes to encourage young academics to participate at the workshops. We would also like to suggest that the lecturer should be informed in advance about the particular situation in (Slovenian) science so she/he could be even more concrete in applying her/his knowledge to the particular national situation and the work in a group would give better results. Another learning point that we gained is that young academics are very interested in this kind of workshops, especially those who would like to continue their research work and stay in academia. All participants agreed on organising similar workshops as a regular practice.

What feedback did you get from participants?

The feedback from participants was positive in general. The majority of researchers were pleased or very pleased with the workshop and they all agreed on organising similar workshops as a regular practice. They showed affection towards the lecturer: “Nice lecturer who speaks with charisma about her experience. Due to her experience, she is credible to give a lecture on this topic.” Participants have expressed an interest for future workshops with similar issues and suggested a few workshops with more specific topics, for example: writing an article, project application, speaking in front of an audience. The critique of the workshop was mainly focused on the fact that some information was “repeating of the already known” and that it was “too general”. Some participants pointed out that the lecturer should be more familiar with the specific Slovenian problems and local specialities to be able to help in the process of forming more useful suggestions for improvements. Participants gave feedback on the workshop while pointing out that it gave them a valuable new perspective. To point out a few: they gained different approaches to career development, awareness of the importance of international networking, knowledge regarding applying for projects and a copyright problem in online publishing, etc.

What was specific for your context, which future workshop leaders need to take into account?

The participants were very interested to get informed on how to get a grant/funding. The lecturer advised them to inform themselves on who else also applied for the grant, so they will know how competitive they are and to think about who the reviewers of their application are. The reason why the audience was mostly interested in funding is the specific Slovenian context and the situation in the scientific sphere, which future leaders of the working group need to take into account. After Slovenia’s independence (1991), the process of introducing the capitalist logic and acceptance of neoliberal paradigms started gradually, which led to ‘managerialism’ in Slovenian science and research, and the construction of excellence based on the global academic system, which is based on the Western norm of meritocracy. The inclusion of Slovenian research centres and universities in the system for obtaining EU funds and the introduction of the continuous measurement of the internationally comparable quality of researchers, research groups, research institutions and universities have brought about a shift in the emphasis from the quality of research to the quantity of published articles in highly-rated journals, which only count when written in English.

Slovenia is a small country with a small system. According to the results of some studies, this is a disadvantage. The traditional Slovenian scientific habitus is also problematic. The infrastructure still needs to be constructed. There is a unique system of financing in Slovenia, because 80% of the budget comes from national or international calls. Unfortunately, projects have become a fundamental form of research work in Slovenian science, especially at the research institutes, and the struggle for funding has become the main preoccupation of researchers in order to survive. The result of the economic and social crisis from 2008 and the related reforms from 2012 (Fiscal Balance Act) have caused research funds to be cut each year and prolongation of the dates of national calls for research proposals, which caused an uncertain financial situation in scientific institutions. Furthermore, financing mostly depends on quantitative merits and usually

money for research goes to people who have the best conditions to publish articles, though they are not necessarily also the best researchers. Another huge problem is also that the projects are strongly lobbied and there is no objective evaluation and selection. Consequently, funding is currently one of the main concerns of young academics in Slovenia.

5.4 CONCLUSION

Compare the set-up and evaluation of the workshops in the two departments. What similarities and what differences did you encounter?

The workshop was performed only at ZRC SAZU due to the lack of interest from the Biotechnical Faculty. However, it is worth to point out that participants also came from the STEM departments (institute) that are situated at ZRC SAZU. The discussion did not show any differences among them because STEM participants were not active in the debate. Concerning the problems with the agency and the scientific excellence criteria, we are all facing similar problems.

To what extent do you see the workshops as a feasible instrument to create or increase gender awareness among appointment committee members?

We largely see the workshop as a feasible instrument to create and increase gender awareness among appointment committee members. Due to other issues present in the Slovenian scientific sphere, the gender issue was one of the important topics, but not the only one. In our opinion, if we expose gender too much, participants do not attend workshops and they do not participate in the debate. This (and other) reasons forced us to strategically perform the workshop in a way that gender was only one criteria among several others (finances/grants, networking, administrative support), because in Slovenia, questions connected to gender are only at the stage of 'raising awareness'. In addition, the lecturer should be more familiar with the question of gender and to be able to clearly distinguish the topic of gender inequalities from other topics connected with the issue of scientific excellence. Furthermore, we as organisers (the GARCIA team) should be more proactive in leading the workshop, especially the discussion, and remind the lecturer during her lectures to focus on gender issues more often.

Nevertheless, lecture highlighted some general issues from gender problems and exposed that due to the globalisation of the research market, competition is science environment huge, and many people are willing to move to get a job in academia or leave the academia. Women are particularly affected due to their biological clock. In addition, the lecturer made a very important statement while saying that if you are a female, you will much harder get an academic position due to the fewer positions in academia, especially if you come from a black minority. The discussion on these issues provided us with very important information about the understanding of gender, which always needs to be understood through the intersectional perspective – at the crossroads of other social/academic phenomena and together with class, ethnicity, age, etc.

While talking about gender issues, the lecturer pointed out that women who get promoted do not necessarily get the external network in order to progress, but men usually do. While talking about performing research, the lecturer stressed the meaning of a good mentor and paid particular attention to the problem of fewer grants for women in science. The participants agreed that there should be more public discussions about gender emancipation and values that each gender embodies, and how to use this knowledge to optimise successful teamwork and improve Slovenian science.

6. SWITZERLAND

6.1 INTRODUCTION

Because the UNIL, like other Swiss higher education (HE) institutions more generally, has been very sensitive to the problems faced by postdoc researchers, we decided to take the existing actions at the UNIL in favour of postdocs as the starting point for our GARCIA Action plan. Therefore, we adapted the guidelines provided by the Dutch team for task 7.3.2 according to the local situation. In fact, as noted previously (cf. reports for tasks 7.1 and 7.2) the very definition of the category of “postdoc” in the Swiss context is rather complicated. Furthermore, many actions in favour of postdocs were undertaken by the UNIL central services during the period of the GARCIA project. Therefore, a wide range of training and support measures was organised for the whole of UNIL and we decided, in our self-tailored GARCIA action plan, to collaborate with some particular actions (as we also did for WP6 and the mentoring programme) instead of organising specific sessions whose content would have overlapped considerably with various other actions, workshops, training sessions, etc.

6.1.1 Swiss context

The rapid and profound changes in terms of numerical expansion, internationalisation, standardisation and the implementation of the Bologna reform in the Swiss context have had a major impact on the early stages of academic careers. Over the last decade much attention has been paid in Switzerland to the monitoring of doctoral training. Since 2000 numerous doctoral programmes have been created, although they were not matched by a growth in postdoctoral career possibilities in the academic field. The situation of postdocs has therefore attracted some interest, particularly over the past five years. However, the precarious working conditions of Swiss young researchers (known as *Nachwuchs* in German and *relève académique* in French¹) has far-reaching effects not only on people’s personal trajectories, but also on disciplines and institutions.

As the Swiss academic employment structure is very “bottom heavy,” there are few professorships (or tenured equivalent positions) and a very large number of fixed-term teaching and research positions that are usually seen as offering a “stepping stone” towards an academic career, but which do not necessarily lead on to a professorship within 10 or 15 years after the PhD. There are therefore multiple ramifications and combinations of the seemingly endless loop of insecure postdoc positions.

Providing support for Swiss “young researchers” was one of the three main objectives set by the Federal Council (the Swiss government) in the legislative agenda of the Ministry for Education, Research and Innovation for 2012-2015 (SER, 2012).

Defining, counting and managing postdocs

On the Swiss “young researchers’ academic portal” (*portail relève académique*)² hosted by the University of Neuchâtel, the following definition of a “postdoc” is proposed: “The

¹ We propose to use the term “young researcher” in English to translate these generic terms used in German and French to designate a person who is potentially able to embark on an academic career track.

² https://www2.unine.ch/releve/page-24525_en.html (accessed July 27, 2016).

term postdoc designates a phase of academic qualification postdating the doctorate, the institutional forms of which vary according to the discipline. The postdoc is most prevalent in the natural sciences and technical sciences. With the increase in third party funding of research – either through research projects or grants – this type of appointment is starting to spread to the human and social sciences. Generally, a postdoctoral researcher is employed on a fixed-term contract for research projects at a university.”³ [...] “The postdoctoral phase is considered as a period during which to develop research projects and the necessary skills for becoming independent senior researchers.”⁴ In the German-speaking part of Switzerland, postdoc status may end when people get their *Habilitation* while in the French-speaking part the frontier is more blurred.

In 2014, *Horizon* (no. 102),⁵ the journal of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), an article was published showing that postdoc positions are not as exciting as they might seem to be at first glance. “How postdocs are exploited” is the teaser on the front page, while the article is entitled “The invisible achievers”.

Figure 6.1. Front page of *Horizon* (2014: 102).

The sentence highlighted, in the article, after the title says: “Postdocs on temporary contracts are responsible for a large proportion of research in Switzerland. But only ten percent of them manage to get a permanent job at a university. A career in academia has to become more attractive”.

³ https://www2.unine.ch/releve/page-24578_en.html (accessed July 27, 2016).

⁴ https://www2.unine.ch/releve/page-24579_en.html (accessed July 27, 2016).

⁵ http://www.snf.ch/SiteCollectionDocuments/horizonte/Horizonte_gesamt/Horizons_102_E.pdf (accessed July 27, 2016).

Some observers (such as, for example, Caspar Hirschi in the *Neue Zürcher Zeitung* – one of the most-read Swiss-German newspapers – entitled “Paradebeispiel einer Scheinreform,” May 28th 2015⁶) speak of a “postdoc bubble”, because academic systems (all around the world and not only in Switzerland) have produced many PhD holders during the last decade and the academic market cannot absorb them all. For Hirschi the “Swiss universities are inflating the postdoc bubble by offering so many PhD positions.”

As shown in Figure 2, the number of postdocs has greatly increased at the UNIL over the last five years (+ 21% for PhD students and + 29% for postdocs).

Figure 6.2. Number of PhD students and postdocs at the UNIL between 2010 and 2014. Source: Workshop “Postdocs@UNIL: What’s new”, Lausanne, UNIL, 18.11.2015.

To tackle the situation of “young researchers” several reports and studies have been written during the last years and they all point towards the difficulty of getting figures regarding the number of postdocs. Among the most frequently cited are:

- Fink, A., Hirschi, C., Hirt, M., Paszkowski, U., Mayer, I., & Maeder, P. (2012). *VISION 2020. Position Paper of a Young Researchers’ Group. Hearing WBK-S.*
- CSST (2013). “Encourager la relève pour favoriser l’innovation en Suisse”
- SERI - State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (2014). *Mesures pour encourager la relève scientifique en Suisse*
- CSSI (2015). Cultures de promotion doctorale et modèles de *tenure track* dans les universités suisses.

The *Horizon* article states that: “At the request of parliament, the Federal Council presented a report last May [SERI 2014] in which it was assumed that there are currently

⁶ <http://www.nzz.ch/meinung/debatte/paradebeispiel-einer-scheinreform-1.18550103>

between 5,000 and 8,000 postdocs [working in Swiss universities]. ‘That’s undoubtedly too small a number,’ says the bioinformatician João Martins, who surveyed some 400 Swiss research groups for the SNSF. He reckons that the number of postdocs lies between 12,000 and 14,000. In that case, there would be at least three postdocs for every one of the roughly 4,000 professors in Switzerland.”

In fact, the ratio between fixed-term positions and permanent positions in Swiss universities is one of the principal problems identified for Swiss postdocs:

Figure 6.3. Composition of academic employees across all Swiss universities

The Swiss “young researchers’ academic portal” confirms that: “In the [hard] sciences in particular, a succession of postdoctoral positions lasting more than six years is not recommended. When four to six years have elapsed after the doctorate, the person is expected to occupy a position as group leader and acquire their own [research] funds. In some fields, the postdoctoral career is shorter (one year maximum, or does not exist at all, especially in the economic and social sciences).”⁷

One structural point to be addressed is that of the incentive to become an independent researcher as early in the career as possible and the fact that postdoc positions are usually subordinate positions (to a tenured professor). The new four-year frame programme of the SNSF for 2017-2020 encourages young researchers to become independent more quickly, but says nothing about increasing the number of tenured positions available for them to fill.

6.1.2 Situation of postdocs

In line with the policies and reflections conducted at the federal level, the UNIL mentioned the situation of “young researchers” in its strategic plan for 2012-2016, creating a new Vice-Rectorate in charge of junior academic careers (“young researchers”) and diversity, and a Consultative Commission for “young researchers” A

⁷ https://www2.unine.ch/releve/page-24579_en.html (accessed July 27, 2016).

survey was conducted among UNIL postdocs in 2013, and on March 27th 2014, this Vice-Rectorate and the “young researchers” Commission organised a meeting for the launch of the report on postdocs at the UNIL (“*Résultat de l’enquête auprès de la relève postdoctorale de l’UNIL*”⁸) written on the basis of the survey. During this event (in which several members of the GARCIA team participated), it became very clear that the postdocs who had received the invitation to answer the survey (N=408, of whom 231 persons replied) did not represent all postdocs hired at the UNIL.

In fact, “postdocs” can be hired at very different stages in their academic careers (e.g. just after having obtained their PhD or many years later, having already occupied several other “postdoc” positions, in Switzerland or abroad) and on positions that are not necessarily clearly identified as “postdoc”. Therefore, during the launch event the “hidden” postdocs took the opportunity to raise awareness of their existence and their “invisibility”. The survey had been sent to the following categories of persons considered members of the “young researchers” community by the UNIL: PhD Assistants, Senior SNSF Researchers, Junior Lecturers and Assistant Professors with or without tenure track (categories in yellow in Table 1). But the discussion revealed that some Senior Lecturers consider themselves to be “young researchers” as well as some of the Senior Researchers who may be on either permanent or non-permanent positions (categories in green in Table 1).

⁸ <https://www.unil.ch/researcher/files/live/sites/researcher/files/shared/Rapport.pdf> (accessed July 27, 2016).

Table 6.1. Categories of academic employees at the UNIL

Academic status (French)	Categories of academic employees (French)	UNIL abbrev. (French)	Translation
Corps professoral	Professeur.e ordinaire et associé.e	PO & PA	Full and Associate Professor (tenured)
	Professeur.e assistant.e en PTC	PAST – PTC	Assistant Professor with tenure track
	Professeur.e assistant.e	PAST	Assistant Professor without tenure track
Corps intermédiaire	Maître.s.sse d'enseignement et de recherche	MER	Senior Lecturer (tenured)
	Maître et Maîtresse assistant.e	MA	Junior Lecturer
	1 ^{er} Assistant.e	1er Ass.	PhD Assistant – Postdoc
	Assistant.e diplômé.e	Ass. Dip.	Teaching Assistant – PhD Student
	Doctorant.e SNSF	Doc SNSF	Research Assistant – PhD Student
Personnel administratif et technique (PAT)	Responsable/Chargé de recherche	No official abbreviations	Senior Researcher
	Chercheur.e SNSF Senior		Senior SNSF Researcher
	Chercheur.e SNSF Junior		Junior SNSF Researcher (without PhD)
	Collaborateur / collaboratrices scientifiques et administratives		Other scientific staff

In order to take all postdocs in account, an Email was sent out after the launch event on October 27th 2014 to invite the persons who considered themselves to belong to the “young researchers” category to register on a dedicated mailing list and fill out a short survey in order to receive information and to fully participate to actions for the “young researchers”. The text of the Email was as follows:

“We have realised that some people (e.g. with an administrative contract or those who are working for the University Teaching Hospital - CHUV) never received information linked to UNIL postdocs and non-tenured faculty. Some others may be interested in receiving this information in order to pass it on within their institute / department.

If this is your case and you want to receive information concerning UNIL postdocs and untenured faculty members, please complete the small form on this page [link].

*This mailing list will be managed by the Junior Faculty Development Committee and will only generate a limited number of Emails.
Thank you for your cooperation and best regards.”*

After the publication of this first report, the young academics of the various faculties discussed the implementation of concrete measures, which we describe below, and in particular the creation of a structure to support postdocs and people on academic career tracks. The short name “Graduate Campus” was given to this structure, which is still under construction. A new study was carried out to identify the needs of the so-called “*relève académique*” (taking in account all persons who registered as members of the “young researchers” category) in 2015 and it showed the huge diversity within this category. As indicated in our previous WP7 reports (Kradolfer & Le Feuvre, 2016), the category “postdoc” at the UNIL which covers at least four distinct employment statuses:

- **Postdoc assistants**, who are recruited to perform teaching and research duties (usually in some kind of combination), and who are funded through the main cantonal budget (i.e. structural funds). The employment contracts are fixed-term, with a 1 + 2 + 2 format (a 12-month contract to begin with, potentially followed by two successive 24-month contracts). It is not possible to have more than one (5-year) postdoc assistantship within the same institution, but there is nothing to stop an individual moving to a second position in a different university. It is not possible for a former PhD Assistant to be recruited directly as postdoc assistant at the UNIL; he or she must first spend at least one year in another institution (preferably abroad), before returning to the UNIL.
- **Postdoc researchers** (usually called “SNSF Senior” postdoc positions), who are recruited to work on externally funded research projects. The duration of these positions is determined by the 3rd party funding available, but is usually for 12 to 24 months. Generally speaking, these positions do not involve any teaching duties. Most of them are funded via competitive SNSF research project funding; other funding sources (e.g. Foundations) are more frequent in some faculties than in others.
- In addition to these main “postdoc” positions, people with PhDs can also be recruited to temporary (PAST) or “tenure track” (PAST PTC) **Assistant professorships** and/or temporary (MA) or “tenure track” (MA > MER) **Senior Lectureships**. These are extremely rare in both the STEM and SHS Faculties and represent a negligible proportion of all postdocs at the UNIL and in Switzerland more generally. In some cases, these positions are funded (directly to the candidates themselves, as it were) through the SNSF programme to support young researchers. Much like the European Science Foundation schemes, the SNSF Ambizione and SNSF Professorship programmes enable “promising,” highly selected young researchers to receive a funding package, which includes their own salary and money to cover research costs (usually including salaries for at least one PhD student or postdoc) and to take this to the institution of their choice.
- Finally, an undetermined number of “postdocs” can be recruited to work on (usually externally funded) research projects on **Technical and Administrative**

Staff (PAT) contracts which may be either permanent or fixed-term, full or part-time. Of all the postdocs in Switzerland, this is probably the most “hard to reach” category, notably because the content of their work is not necessarily seen as directly related to academic endeavours, although we know that this is often the case in practice. This is one of the strategies that can be adopted in order to continue employing postdoc assistants who have already completed their 5-year contract and who still do not have any other employment opportunities outside the UNIL.

In 2015, there were approximately 400 full-time equivalent postdoc assistantships and FNS-funded postdocs working at the UNIL. The University statistics do not enable us to calculate the precise share of each of these types of contract, nor the gender composition of this “postdoc” workforce. The main postdoc categories (postdoc Assistants + SNSF Senior postdocs) make up 10.8% of staff in the SSP (SHS) Faculty, as compared with 22.4% in the STEM (FBM) Faculty. However, much of this difference is explained by the larger share of PhDs (and smaller share of tenured positions) in the social than in the medical sciences.

The results of the postdoc survey of 2013 show that the mean age of postdocs is 35.2 years (ranging from 26 to 55 years) and that they come from 45 different countries; there are almost as many women (203) as men (205). 13% of the respondents do not know their job description and 8% consider that it does not reflect the reality of their work. 84% of the respondents work longer than indicated in the contract. 21% would like to have more information regarding the academic career path. 20% get no or only limited feedback on their work. 50% of fathers and 53% of mothers have difficulties with WLB.

Some interesting points for GARCIA were raised regarding working conditions and careers in the responses to various questions (in brackets, the number of persons who wrote such a comment):

- Positions promised at 100% but paid at 80% or 90% (4)
- Contracts with only short working hours (60% of a full-time position or less) requiring multiple contracts (1)
- Mandatory teaching activities not specified in the contract (1)
- Job description not respected by the UNIL (1), illegal contract (1), past teaching / research experience not taken into account in the postdoc contract (1), contradiction between the contract and its annex (1)
- Postdoc position not clearly defined (1)
- Heavy workload intruding on personal life (4)
- Family life incompatible with demand for mobility (2)
- Temporary contract increases pressure when one has family commitments (2)
- Difficulties in envisaging starting a family when on fixed-term contracts (4)
- Problem related to part-time work (2): not always accepted by the superior, who expects scientific output of someone working at 100%
- Rather poor pay (2): cannot afford childminder; only income for whole family
- On a fixed-term contract it is not possible to submit projects to the SNSF (3)

Additional problems not directly linked to the working conditions where cited:

- Difficulties in finding accommodation in Lausanne (7)

- Difficulties in finding a crèche (6)

6.1.3 Existing workshops for postdocs

A study for the setting up of the Graduate Campus was published internally in 2016 by the Vice-Rectorate in charge of junior academic careers, on the basis of consultations with the faculties, the central services and post-doc associations, in order to identify needs of the “young researchers”. The report lists the workshops already existing for the “young researchers” and we report here those addressed to postdocs only:

- REGARD Programme (considered as a mentoring programme): “The REGARD programme offers workshops for young female academics and for women professors of the universities of French-speaking Switzerland. Its aim is to develop competences and to propose concrete tools for career management and supervision. These workshops also create opportunities for discussion and the exchange of experiences between women researchers. They also aim to increase awareness about gender equality in the academic career.”⁹
- Scientific English / Academic writing
- Being mobile as a couple or a family
- Dual-career couples (DCC)
- How to fund your research through the EU and foundations
- (for FBM) PhD and Postdoc Meeting: Enter your most exciting work in the competition and present your work at Novartis in Basel
- (for FBM) HBA Networking event: "Creating your Elevator Pitch"
- (for FBM) Transforming the pharmaceutical industry: how to stay ahead
- (for FBM) Annual Allergy and Immunology Meeting: 2016 Young Researchers sessions

One of the aims of the Graduate Campus is to complete the offer for workshops and services directed to the postdocs at the UNIL. Amongst the new actions undertaken or to be undertaken in the next Strategic Plan of the UNIL for 2017-2020 are:

- Workshop: Creating the postdoc’s job-hunt package: finding opportunities outside the university and preparing applications
- Workshop: Preparing to apply for an academic job
- Workshop: Training in Project Management: designing and managing a project from the first trigger to the closing phase
- Workshop: Defining your professional profile
- Clarify the missions of the Welcome Centre and reinforce this structure to offer better local integration and information for newcomers (website, help desk, welcome events, etc.)
- Offer more administrative and informative documents in English
- Reinforce the alumni network
- Support measures for event organisation by postdocs for postdocs
- Support measures for entrepreneurship
- Offering more skills assessments

⁹ See: <http://www.unifr.ch/regard/en/enbref/presentation> (accessed July 27, 2016).

Various information flyers for postdocs are available on the “Research Career” webpage¹⁰ (under different categories: Financing your postdoc at the UNIL; Starting at the UNIL; Organising your postdoc abroad; Research development; Teaching at the UNIL; Developing your skills; Associations, Networks and Support; Career; Charters and Ethics).

6.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

As can be seen from the list of problems identified by the “young researchers” (at the end of point 1.2), some structural and organisational problems cannot be solved in workshops (individual support being already well addressed through various the mentoring programmes) but need collective action through associations and/or trade unions. Although the consultation for the Graduate Campus showed that the offer of workshops should be increased, we were not able to identify any important areas that were not already covered.

Discussion with the Board of the Association of the intermediate body and the doctoral students of the UNIL (ACIDUL) showed that workshops on sexual or moral harassment might be useful, but since this was obviously not a problem for postdocs in particular, we decided not to pursue such a project.

Another point raised by ACIDUL was the fact that people are not clearly informed about their duties and rights regarding their working conditions, we collaborated in the organisation of a round table on November 18th 2015 on the job descriptions for all members of the UNIL. This was also the launch event for an Internet platform for information exchange on job descriptions (<http://wp.unil.ch/acidul/action-cahiers-des-charges>). Sabine Kradolfer gave a talk on this occasion based on data and information collected for GARCIA.

¹⁰ <https://www.unil.ch/researcher/home.html> (accessed July 27, 2016),

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DES CHARGES 2015**

Conférence publique sur les conditions
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Lancement de l'action
Cahier des charges 2015

**MERCREDI 18 NOVEMBRE
ANTHROPOLE AUDITOIRE 2097**

16h00 – Introduction, recommandations et lancement de l'action
16h30 – Conférence publique, débat, questions.
18h00 – Apéritif

INVITÉ.E.S

Sabine Kradolfer – *sociologue, UNIL*
Joanne Chassot – *membre de l'ACIL, maître assistante, UNIL*
Raphaël Ramuz – *secrétaire syndical, Syndicat des services publics (SSP)*
Alexandre Curchod – *avocat, spécialiste du droit du travail*

ACIDUL
Association du corps intermédiaire et des
doctorant.e.s de l'Université de Lausanne

Figure 6.4. Flyer of the round table on job descriptions

The GARCIA team also participated in the “young researchers” Commission which developed a tool in 2015 for postdoctoral professional career development in the form of a self-assessment questionnaire: “The self-assessment questionnaire is intended specifically for postdocs. It is meant to facilitate an annual assessment of your current position, aid reflection on your accomplishments and help you identify what is required for progress towards your professional goals. After you finish your self-assessment, it is recommended to discuss it with a resource person such as a department head, a project principal applicant, a professor, or a mentor.”¹¹ We were asked to provide expert feedback on various drafts of these documents.

¹¹ <https://www.unil.ch/researcher/home/menuint/post-doc--ma-prof-assistant/carriere.html> (accessed July 27, 2016).

Sabine Kradolfer was also asked by members of the organisation committee of the 2015 Annual Meeting of the Swiss Ethnological Society to run a plenary session with a round table on postdocs. This event was held at the University of Bern on November 14th 2015, with the title: “The Postdoc Hamster Wheel: Round table on the situation of anthropology postdocs in Switzerland.” Four postdocs at either an early or an advanced stage of their careers took part:

- Giada de Coulon, School of Social Work Fribourg, University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland
- Jérémie Forney, Anthropology Institute, University of Neuchâtel
- Esther Leemann, Department of Ethnology, University of Lucerne
- Alessandra Pellegrini, University of Applied Studies, Bern

The audience was very active during the round table and discussions were very interesting, showing considerable fear on the part of the postdocs regarding their opportunities to follow an academic career path with so much uncertainty.

6.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

A general problem identified by ACIDUL and also by UNIL central services and in our research for GARCIA is that our target population (postdocs and persons with non-permanent positions) are asking for more workshops on different topics and sometimes, workshops may already exist either at the UNIL or outside (for example, the CUSO - Conférence universitaire de Suisse occidentale / University conference from Western Switzerland – offers a transversal programme to develop generic skills). Therefore a compilation of the complete offer of workshops should be published or information on all offers should be sent to all postdocs. Usually such information is provided when the persons start to work at the UNIL and tends to get lost in the quantity of practical knowledge that needs to be assimilated at that time. Therefore information is getting lost because it doesn't necessarily arrive at the right time.

Another point is that people only really start to be conscious of their precariousness when they face problems with their supervisors, the institution or some services, or when they are coming to the end of a contract and realise that there are limited opportunities to remaining in the academic sector because of the lack of permanent positions. The creation of the Graduate Campus could help to solve this problem by centralising all information and offering a help desk that can be contacted when information is needed. Members of the faculty administration can be good sources of advice and support.

6.4 CONCLUSION

It was not always easy to make a clear distinction between mentoring actions for GARCIA's WP6 and the WP7 workshops for junior researchers or those of WP4, as they intersect and overlap to a certain extent. For example, the REGARD programme organises workshop that have also be cited in the WP6 report as they are considered to be a mentoring programme.

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